

Fast then Slow: Choice Revisions Drive a Decline in the Attraction Effect*

Alexia Gaudeul[†] Paolo Crosetto^{‡§}

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Abstract

We explore the nature and robustness of the attraction effect. The attraction effect can be seen as a persistent bias or as the result of heuristics that may not persist upon reflection. We provide robust experimental evidence that the attraction effect first rises and then falls over time when participants are incentivized to make a quick choice they can later revise. Participants in two experiments under continuous time pressure make choices among options with the aim to maximize an objective, measurable value. We find that participants disproportionately favor the asymmetrically dominant option in the first seconds to then revise their choices until the effect disappears or is significantly reduced. The effect survives only in the special and often studied case of indifference among options. We develop a tractable extension to the Multi-attribute Linear Ballistic Accumulator model to allow for choice revisions. That model explains how choice revisions reduce context effects. We estimate its parameters at the individual level, and document differences between fast and slow participants that also play a role in explaining the rise-and-fall pattern in the attraction effect. We extend the analysis to similarity and compromise effects. We find a very small similarity effect, which does not exhibit any dynamics, and a significant reverse compromise effect displaying a rise-and-fall pattern. Our findings, while limited to objective-value tasks, are consistent with context effects being a short-term heuristics that can be superseded by more reflective cognitive strategies when decision-makers have time and incentive to do so.

Keywords: asymmetric dominance, attraction effect, induced preferences, choice process, time constraint, rationality, heuristic, context effects

JEL: C91; D12; D83

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[†]Competence Centre for Behavioural Insights, Joint Research Centre, European Commission, 1050 Brussels, Belgium. email: alexia.gaudeul@ec.europa.eu

[‡]Univ. Grenoble Alpes, INRAE, CNRS, Grenoble INP, GAEL, 38000 Grenoble, France. email: paolo.crosetto@inra.fr

[§]The order of authors is certified random, see [Ray and Robson \(2018\)](#).

1 Introduction

Choice among options can be influenced by their context in ways that make no sense from a rational point of view. This phenomenon is known as a *context effect* and was first evidenced by Tversky (1972). The best known and most widely documented of those context effect is the *attraction effect*, also known as the *decoy* or *asymmetric dominance effect* ("AE", Huber et al., 1982). Under the AE, adding an option (*the decoy*) that is clearly dominated by another option in a choice set increases the likelihood that this option (*the target*) will be chosen at the expense of the other option (*the competitor*).

We aim to determine if the AE is a short-term phenomenon, which disappears when individuals are given time and incentives to revise their choices, or is a persistent feature of choice. We therefore elicit both fast, intuitive responses and reflective, slow revisions of the initial responses, within the same choice tasks and for the same individuals. We do not focus on what a fast and slow choice, separately, will look like; nor on what kind of choices fast and slow decision makers make. Rather, we focus on whether, when and how decision makers under continuous time pressure move from fast to slow decision modes, revising their choices expressed in the early stages of the decision process.

Determining the nature of context effects is relevant to several ongoing debates in psychology, economics and decision making. It relates to recent literature in experimental economics focusing on the importance of error and cognitive uncertainty, and their role in choice revisions (Nielsen and Rehbeck, 2022; Enke and Graeber, 2019; Benjamin et al., 2020). It also uses concepts from dual-process theories of choice in psychology (Evans and Stanovich, 2013; Kahneman, 2011). It further contributes to the debate in marketing and decision making on the persistence of context effects and on the link between choice and the speed of decision (Cataldo and Cohen, 2020; Pettibone, 2012).

We rely on a novel and intuitive objective-value, induced-preferences expenditure minimization task that allows us to measure the AE not only when options are indifferent – as done by the bulk of the existing literature – but also when they differ in value. This choice task can be naturally extended to examine other context effects, such as the similarity and compromise effects. We further apply a continuous-time-pressure choice-process elicitation mechanism, originally due to Caplin et al. (2011), to elicit, for each subject and each choice task, what she thinks is the best choice at any given time. This allows us to obtain *both* a subject's fast, intuitive, heuristic choice, and her slower, reflective, compensatory choice, as well when the subject switches choice. We finally develop an original extension of the Multi-Attribute Linear Ballistic Accumulator model (MLBA, Trueblood et al., 2014) to jointly analyze choices, revisions, and response times. This model integrates choice revisions into the MLBA and allows us to fully exploit our data within a widely used structural model. Original modeling and choice task, and an innovative elicitation mechanism combine into a comprehensive stack of tools that can be readily extended to other discrete choice environments, including preference-based or real-product tasks.

We show that the AE is mainly transitory, meaning that the effect follows, on average, a rise-and-fall pattern. The effect is strong in the first few seconds but then declines over a relatively short time span of twenty seconds. This result is robust to variations in stimuli, to different ways to measure the AE, to differences in design in two experiments, to differences in experimental samples (students and general consumers), and to differences in the objective values of options in a choice set. The AE survives as a persistent large effect *only* in the special case in which target and competitor have the same value. This case, where subjects are indifferent, is the dominant focus of the existing literature (Huber et al., 2014; Lichters et al., 2015). Away from indifference and given enough time and incentives, the AE rises and then falls, to zero in one experiment, and to about a third of the peak in another.

This result is due to two different factors: *choice revisions*, whereby subjects submit a first, fast choice that favors the target and then revise their choices in favor of the competitor over time; and *subject heterogeneity*, whereby fast, intuitive subjects make quick choices in favor of the target in the

first seconds, while slower, reflective subjects start choosing later and are less subject to the AE, thus eroding the effect over time in the aggregate. Using our original extension of the MLBA with revisions, we provide aggregate and individual-level estimations of the intensity and dynamic patterns of the attraction effect. We show that similar patterns of rise-and-fall, heterogeneity and revisions also hold for other context effects, to the extent that those context effects arise in our experiments. In particular, we show very limited evidence for a similarity effect, which therefore does not either rise nor fall over time, and strong evidence of a rise-and-fall pattern for a reverse compromise effect, whereby a preference for extreme options appears early on but is reduced over time.

Section 2 surveys the main theoretical approaches to the AE, either as the result of fast heuristic decision making or as a bias that ought to impact also slower, reflective choices. It covers the recent experimental literature investigating the nature of context effects by using time constraints or allowing for choice revisions. Section 3 presents our two experiments. It first introduces our continuous-time-pressure choice-process elicitation mechanism and our objective-value task, and then provides the details and results of the experiments. The first experiment focuses on the AE with a sample of 111 mostly university students, while the second extends our methodology to the similarity and compromise effects with a sample of 198 subjects from the general population. Section 4 introduces our extension of the MLBA model to include choice revisions. We estimate a mixed-effect version of this model using Bayesian methods. This allows us to identify and interpret differences in decision styles across individuals. Section 5 discusses the importance, interpretation and limitations of our results, focusing on their external validity and discussing their implications and potential extension to preference-based tasks.

All data and detailed scripts to reproduce our results are available at the GitHub repository of the paper <https://github.com/paolocrosetto/A-choice-process-explanation-of-the-attraction-effect-data>. All materials for a full replication are available at the OSF page of the project <https://osf.io/xr28d/>.

2 Context and related literature

A debate about the nature of the attraction effect The Attraction Effect has generated an enormous literature since it was first evidenced forty years ago. This is because of its theoretical importance as a direct violation of the axiom of Independence from Irrelevant Alternatives, because of its counter-intuitive nature, and because of its applications in marketing. The AE has been widely replicated in marketing and consumer research (Huber and Puto, 1983; Simonson, 1989; Park and Kim, 2005), cognitive psychology (Trueblood et al., 2013), neuroscience (Hu and Yu, 2014), game theory (Wang et al., 2018), experimental economics (Herne, 1999; Sonsino, 2010; Kroll and Vogt, 2012; Sürücü et al., 2019; Castillo, 2020), and even in some studies on animal behavior (Schuck-Paim et al., 2004; Shafir et al., 2002).

We study the dynamic robustness of the attraction effect, focusing on whether it is a fast heuristic or a deeply rooted bias. Different theoretical approaches to the AE and other context effects support one or the other option.

Several theories of choice predict an attraction effect as a stable feature of choice, independent of the time spent on a task or on the fast or slow nature of the choice. This is the case under reference-dependent utility coupled with loss aversion (Usher and McClelland, 2004), under decision field theory (Roe et al., 2001a), according to salience theory (Bordalo et al., 2013), using the elimination by aspect theory of Tversky (2003), assuming shifting decision weight across attributes (Ariely and Wallsten, 1995), or assuming a form of trade-off aversion (Hedgcock and Rao, 2009). However, those theories, while they explain why an AE may arise, do not do a good job in explaining when it does not arise, as

shown in recent literature that focuses on factors that reduce or mute it.

For instance, the effect is reduced or muted when individuals have information about brands (Ratneshwar et al., 1987), when the product description is unambiguous and precise (Mishra et al., 1993), when the options are presented graphically rather than numerically (Frederick et al., 2014), when the products have negative rather than positive attributes (Malkoc et al., 2013), when individuals are not indifferent among options (Crosetto and Gaudeul, 2016; Farmer et al., 2016), and, with animals, when marginally changing the usual design (Cohen and Santos, 2017). On the other hand, the effect is amplified when individuals are asked to justify their choices (Simonson, 1989) and when the dominance relation is more focal (Król and Król, 2019).

A different approach is therefore needed to rationalize the above literature on the limits in the robustness of the attraction effect. We do so by thinking of the AE as the result of a heuristic. Heuristics are simple, intuitive choice rules that reduce the complexity of a problem by ignoring most information and yet enabling fast decisions that are generally sufficiently good (Gigerenzer et al., 2000). Heuristics are associated with the System 1, “satisficing” (Simon, 1959), “intuitive”, “fast” (Kahneman, 2011), or “non-compensatory” (Tversky, 1972; Dieckmann et al., 2009) thinking modes of dual-mode decision theories, which are compellingly defended and clarified in Evans and Stanovich (2013). Under this view, the AE, despite being a violation of rational choice, can be locally optimal, especially in cases in which there is little information, the signals are noisy, or the cognitive abilities of the decision maker do not allow for sufficient accuracy. The effect’s persistence in time then depends on several factors, such as whether tools from System 2 are applied to a problem (Stanovich and West, 2008). This depends on the nature of the problem and on whether decision-makers recognize that that System 1 may profitably be overridden.

Using response times to settle the debate Several studies have focused on response times to determine whether the AE is best understood as a short-term heuristic or as a more stable feature of human choice. Existing studies mostly relied on either 1) imposing time constraints for decision, 2) eliciting or manipulating the decision styles of the individuals, or 3) recording the time at which a decision is made while not imposing a time constraint.

Under method 1, Trueblood et al. (2014) look at decisions under time constraint and show a rise in the attraction effect as time pressure is lowered from 1 to 2 and then 5 seconds. Pettibone (2012) also find increasing attraction and compromise effect with time (2, 4, 6, or 8 seconds). As modeled in Trueblood et al. (2014) using the Linear Ballistic Accumulator (LBA) model, high time pressure forces people into choices that allow for neither heuristic nor reflective decision making. With more time, context effects arise as people notice properties of the menus to guide their decision.

Under method 2, Mao and Oppewal (2012) find higher attraction effect among individuals who rely more on intuitive reasoning, as measured with the rational-experiential inventory (REI). Masicampo and Baumeister (2008) and Pocheptsova et al. (2009) find higher attraction effect with participants whose mental resources are depleted after a self-control task. Cognitive strain can also be manipulated with information overload, such as by increasing the number of attributes of alternatives. Payne et al. (1993, p. 36) then observe higher reliance on non-compensatory decision strategies.

Under method 3, Molloy et al. (2019) show that the attraction effect is present for individuals whose speed of decision is intermediate, but not for others. Other effects do not appear to vary with time. Cataldo and Cohen (2020) show that subjects’ relatively fast decisions display lower attraction and compromise effect, but higher similarity effect, than their relatively slow decisions.

A further approach, not yet applied to context effects, consists in imposing waiting times to subjects. This has been shown to be effective in triggering less impatient and more time-balanced choices, in the

lab and in the field [Imas et al. \(2022\)](#), and in healthier food choices [Brownback et al. \(2022\)](#).

This existing body of work suffers from several drawbacks. Extreme time pressure might induce intuitive replies¹ but gives no time to revise choices, thus barring the researchers from observing choice revisions and transitions to more deliberate thinking modes. Moreover, no method mentioned above allows researchers to easily see how people combine decision styles when making decisions. There may be individuals who make preliminary, fast decisions and then revise those decisions if given more time; others who make fast decisions following their “gut instinct” and are unwilling to revise them; and yet others who do not trust their first impulse and take their time until they reach more deliberate decisions.

Eliciting choice revisions to move further In this paper we instead provide a method fine-tuned to focus on choice revisions. Choice revisions are an important and until recently rather understudied component to understand choice and the formation of preferences. In our context, they allow us to rise above the debate about whether context effects are “fast” or “slow”, by showing how they survive, or not, the transition from fast to slow. Revisions in choice have been investigated empirically in [Benjamin et al. \(2020\)](#); [Nielsen and Rehbeck \(2022\)](#), who let people make choices across lotteries and then let them reconsider their choices after making it clear when those contradict expected utility axioms. They find that people revise their choices to be more consistent with those axioms, thus showing that first choices represent mistakes rather than actual preferences. [Cherchye et al. \(2020\)](#) examine variability in food choice across time on the basis that consistency in behavior indicates better fit with preferences, while variability might indicate choices that are more dependent on the context and less under self-control. They find that poorer, younger and more impulsive individuals exhibit more variability in their choice. This correlates with research showing that poverty impedes cognitive function ([Mani et al., 2013](#)). On the theory side, [Ferreira \(2018\)](#) proposes that “confirmed choices” be used as an alternative to the notion of context-independent or reason-based choice. The choices that people do not wish to revise may be used as a practical proxy of welfare.

We propose that a first step in choice is subject to context effects and consists in eliminating less favored options from the choice set. This elimination operates according to some heuristics, such as dominance editing, and results in a bias for some options, such as the dominant option in the attraction effect. A second, subsequent step in choice operates on the reduced subset of options that results from the first step. The context in this second step is different from that in the first step, so that resulting revised choices tend to reduce the context effect that results from first choices.

3 Two experiments

We ran two experiments for this paper, the first focusing on the attraction effect, the other generalizing our findings to other context effects. The design of choice sets and details in the presentation of options differed across experiments.

3.1 General methods

We focus in this section on things that are common to both experiments, in particular the task participants had, the way this task was presented, and the way we elicited choice using a continuous-time-pressure choice-process mechanism. Details in the implementation, the subject pool and the design of

¹or it might merely induce subjects to fall back to the strategy developed in the usually not time-constrained instructions phase, see [Crosetto and Guth \(2021\)](#).

choice sets are given in Sections 3.2 and 3.3.

An expenditure minimization task

Participants performed an intuitive *expenditure minimization task*. Their objective was to buy a fixed amount of gasoline from the different offers on display. They were given a fixed budget to do this and kept whatever they did not spend on gasoline as their payoff. The goal of participants was thus to choose the cheapest prices per liter, but this was not shown to them. Rather, options were presented as a quantity Q and a price P for each option, and the goal was to choose the option with the lowest price per liter P/Q . Participants had to perform this task several times, whereby menus of options included either two or three options, and quantity was shown either graphically, thus requiring participants to make an estimate of Q , or numerically. The price per liter was not shown, and the quantity and price of each option varied across screens.

This design replicates most features of traditional AE designs, but within an induced-value setting where an objectively better option can be computed. This allows us to overcome most of the limits of traditional designs used to study context effects, at the price of moving away from homegrown preferences and into the realm of objective (but fuzzy) value comparisons. While most of the context effects literature relies on preference-based tasks, recent studies on the cognitive underpinnings of the effects have increasingly relied on objective-value tasks, as [Trueblood et al. \(2013\)](#) using rectangles or [Spektor et al. \(2019\)](#) using pixel-art matrices.

Traditional AE designs propose a choice among items defined over two dimensions (location and size of apartments, quality and price of beers, resolution and durability of TV-sets) and participants must assess the utility trade-off of the two dimensions. Our task allows us to move the difficulty of combining multi-dimensional attributes from the (unobserved and not measurable) utility space to the cognitive difficulty of making price/size evaluations over (measurable) money. The presence of money allows us to evacuate preferences and objectively measure performance. The task is mono-dimensional – participants care about one dimension only, unit price P/Q , but the cognitive difficulty of comparing different quantities and prices makes it two-dimensional, as long as the quantity/price evaluations involved are not trivial.

Our design allows us to seamlessly change incentives by varying the price of options and observing the behavior of participants at the indifference point – as in most of the existing literature – but also away from it – as done for instance by [Farmer et al. \(2016\)](#); [Crosetto and Gaudeul \(2016\)](#). Furthermore, our design allows us to measure the attraction effect not only as an aggregate (between-subjects) effect but as an individual (within-subjects) effect, as we can compare decisions made for objectively similar menus that only differ in their context. This in turn allows us to go deeper in examining individual heterogeneity. While the bulk of the literature has relied on between-subjects designs, more recent studies focusing on the mechanisms and modeling of context effects have moved to within-subjects designs and estimations, as [Berkowitsch et al. \(2014\)](#); [Noguchi and Stewart \(2014\)](#); [Trueblood et al. \(2013, 2014\)](#); [Cataldo and Cohen \(2019\)](#). [Liew et al. \(2016\)](#) convincingly argue, replicating two previous studies, that subjects heterogeneity is crucial when estimating context effects.

A continuous time pressure choice-process elicitation mechanism

We employ a continuous time pressure choice-process elicitation mechanism originally due to [Caplin et al. \(2011\)](#). This allows us to elicit both fast, time-constrained responses and slow, deliberate revisions. The method applies a random stopping mechanism, which generates continuous time pressure as participants do not know at what point in time their choice will be taken into account. Crucially, this

stopping point is randomly drawn *ex-post*: Subjects face a choice screen for 20 seconds. They choose an option by clicking on it. They can change their mind at any time during the 20 seconds. At the end of the trial, one second is drawn at random, and the option chosen *at that second* is the one that is payoff-relevant. If no option has been chosen at that second, then an option is chosen at random within the menu.

More formally, participants face a choice screen for T seconds. Their choice c_{it} , $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$, is automatically recorded as their most recently chosen option.² At the end of the allotted time, the data obtained from each subject is a vector containing all the choices, $C_i = \{c_{it} | t = 1 \dots T\}$. One time point t is then uniformly drawn, $t \sim U(1, T)$, and the choice recorded at that time c_{it} determines the subject's payoff. If no choice had been submitted by time t , then the participant is assigned a choice at random within the menu.

This elicitation mechanism incentivizes the participants to submit a choice as soon as they think to have improved on choosing at random. This is particularly relevant in the presence of decoys, as those are clearly dominated. A first, fast choice for any option other than the decoy makes sure that the decoy will not be chosen by the random mechanism. Once a first choice is submitted, participants are incentivized to revise and improve, if possible, on their choice; the earlier a participant settles on what he thinks is the best option, the higher the probability that this option will be the one actually implemented; nonetheless, the subject continuously faces an incentive to change his mind upon further reflection. With respect to a normal choice task, participants face continuous time pressure and are incentivized to reveal their view of what is the optimal choice over time. Moreover, with respect to standard time pressure tasks, there is no exogenous time constraint by which a choice has to be made. Rather, subjects are free to be as fast or slow as they wish, depending on their decision style or ability.

Our data allows us to look into the process of revision as people move from fast to slow choices. Indeed, we are able to lay bare and observe the choice *process*, including the revision stage that is hidden in other experimental designs where participants are asked for only one choice, which is final. This peculiar elicitation mechanism has been used elsewhere with the same aim – uncovering the choice process. The method has been used to study intuitive and reflective behavior in a guessing game (Agranov et al., 2015), or to investigate the role of dual processes in generosity (Kessler et al., 2017). Ours is the first paper to bring this method to bear in the context effect literature.

Other methods to track the choice process, such as eye-tracking (Reutskaja et al., 2011; Noguchi and Stewart, 2014) or mouse-tracking (Lohse and Johnson, 1996), allow researchers to see what decision-makers look at, but not what option they think best at each point of time. By incentivizing choice over time, we obtain information about what a participant would have chosen under different degrees of time pressure, without having to exogenously impose a time limit. While this does not give us the level of detail needed to inform elimination-by-aspect models of choice as done by Noguchi and Stewart (2014) using eye tracking, it allows us to directly observe intuitive *and* reflective replies to the same problem from the same subject, and hence to shed light on the decision *processes* underlying context effects.

²Participants do not need to click every second on their most preferred option. They simply click when they want to make a choice, and when they want to change their choice.

3.2 Experiment 1

3.2.1 Methods

Treatments

Participants were exposed to the expenditure minimization task described in Section 3.1. We employ a mixed between- and within-subjects treatment structure.

Between subjects, we vary the stimuli used to visualize the expenditure minimization task. In the *Graphical* treatment (Figure 1, left) the quantity of gasoline of each option was displayed graphically by means of a partially filled jerrycan. The filled part indicated the quantity, and a dashed line indicated the target quantity (3 liters) to be bought. In the *Numeric* treatment (Figure 1, right), the quantity was displayed as a simple number. This variation is inspired by the controversy over the robustness of the AE when the options are presented in a graphical or verbal rather than numerical form (Frederick et al., 2014; Huber et al., 2014; Yang and Lynn, 2014).

Figure 1: Stimuli used in Experiment 1

Within subjects, we vary across repetitions of the base task the relative price of target and competitor. The competitor is allowed to have a price of 85%, 95%, 100%, 105% and 115% of the target price, in a symmetric design. This range includes the special case of indifference that is studied by the bulk of the literature, but allows us to study the attraction effect also in situations in which it has monetary consequences.

Measure of the Attraction effect

Subjects face 20 screens with a target, a competitor and a decoy (Figure 2). The decoy has the same size as the target, making dominance in price easy to spot, while comparing the target and the competitor requires a mental computation of price per liter. We measure the attraction effect as the difference in the choice share of the target and the competitor, at any point in time in the 20 allotted seconds. If the price of the target and the competitor are equal, then we measure $\bar{A}_{ABC} - \bar{B}_{ABC}$, where \bar{A}_{ABC} is the share of option A (the target) within choice set ABC (Figure 3 (a)³). This is the simplest possible measure of the Attraction Effect, but it only works well in the special case of indifference among options, which is the case studied in most of the literature.

³The figure is merely a stylized representation of the problem that abstracts away from actual parameters, and is given as a simple tool to compare our overall design with the existing literature.

Figure 2: A choice set in Experiment 1

When the price of the target is not equal to that of the competitor, then the absolute choice shares move in the direction of the incentives. The difference in the choice shares of the target and of the competitor within a single menu does not then pin down the AE, as it is affected by both the AE and the difference in the value of the options. For instance, if the target is 10% less expensive than the competitor, its higher choice share reflects *both* an attraction effect *and* the relative convenience of the target. We therefore need to extend the simple measure introduced above by comparing the choice share of the target when, say, its price is 85% of that of the competitor, to the choice share of the competitor when *its own* price is 85% of that of the target. That is, we compute $\bar{A}_{AB'C} - \bar{B}''_{AB''C}$, cf. Figure 3, b. By comparing the choice share of option A across those two menus, we keep relative prices equal and thus neutralize the relative price effect. This extension gives us a clean measure of the AE for any level of price difference.

Figure 3: Design and measures of the Attraction Effect

The vertical axis is $\hat{q}_i = \ln(q_i)$ and the horizontal axis is $\hat{p}_i = -\ln(p_i)$. Indifference lines $U = \ln(q_i) - \ln(p_i)$ thus corresponds to all options such that $q/p = e^U$.

For robustness we also include an alternative measure of the AE, using 20 further control screens. Subjects face the same screen two non-consecutive times: once as in Figure 2, and once in a screen where no option plays the role of the decoy. This takes two different forms: in the 3vs2 measure, we drop the decoy, and compute $\bar{A}_{ABC} - \bar{A}_{AB}$ (Figure 3, a). This is akin to the measure that was mostly used, between subjects, in the early days of the attraction effect literature. In the 3vs3 measure, we keep three options, but assign a different size to the decoy, so that it is no more dominated by the target, and compute $\bar{A}_{ABC} - \bar{A}_{ABD}$ (Figure 3, a). Slightly different versions of this measure have been used more recently in the AE literature, for instance by Trueblood et al. (2013) and Farmer et al. (2016). In both cases we measure the AE as the difference in the choice share of the target in a screen with vs. without a clearly dominated decoy. This additional measure can be readily applied to the cases of difference in relative price between the target and the competitor, since it only ever compares shares of the target. Details are given in Appendix B.

Experimental details and procedures

We ran seven experimental sessions involving a total of 111 participants, 63 for the Graphical and 48 for the Numeric treatment. The sessions took place in Grenoble, France, in July 2017. Participants were recruited partly from students at a local engineering and economics school, and partly from the general population with ads in local newspapers as well as from an existing database of potential participants in and around Grenoble, a mid-sized French city with a metro area of about half a million people. The resulting sample was composed at 53% by students, the rest being workers or retired and unemployed. Sample demographics are reported in detail in Table E.1 in Appendix E.

All sessions followed the same script. Upon entering, participants were randomly assigned a code and seated. Instructions were read aloud and displayed on the participants' computer screens. After instructions were read and all questions answered, participants went through 4 practice screens. The screens used different stimuli, but were otherwise identical to the ones used in the main task. Out of the 4 screens, two showed choice sets of three choices with a decoy, one a choice set of three choices with no decoy, and another a choice set of two choices with no decoy. At the end of the 4 practice tasks, subject saw a feedback screen, giving them information about the second randomly chosen to be binding, whether at that second they had or not submitted a choice, their choice at that moment (if no choice, the option randomly chosen by the computer), the total cost of the gasoline and their profit. After all remaining questions, if any, had been answered, participants moved to the main task.

In the main task, participants saw a blank screen with a time counter for four seconds. Then, the stimuli, with no possibility to choose, were shown for further two seconds. Then the screen became active and the time bar at the bottom of the screen started filling up. Participants faced the screen for 20 seconds, during which they could click on any option at any time; then the cycle started again. It took about 20 minutes to cycle through the 40 decision tasks, which were constructed as explain in appendix M.1. The order of the 40 tasks was randomized across participants. The order of the options on the screen was also randomized, but fixed for all participants.

At the end of the main task participants were asked to fill in 5 different questionnaires. These were a socio-demographic questionnaire asking question about gender, education, income, profession; SOEP questions on general attitude to risk (Dohmen et al., 2011), trust Dohmen et al. (2008) and a question measuring loss aversion; a qualitative questionnaire to evaluate participants' understanding of the task and inquire into possible experimenter demand effects; the 3-item Cognitive Reflection Test (CRT) questionnaire (Frederick, 2005); and the Consumer Confusion Proneness questionnaire (Walsh et al., 2007).

The English translation of the original French instructions is in appendix L. The web-based experimental software, written in php, as well as the original French instructions are available upon request.

Participants received a 10€ show-up fee. Moreover, five out of the 40 screens were individually and independently drawn to be payoff relevant. Given this payoff rule, participants could earn up to a theoretical maximum of 15.49€ in addition to the show-up fee. This would happen if they always made the profit maximizing choice and the choice situations with the lowest prices were randomly drawn for payment. In practice, subject earned on average 10.00€ in addition to the show-up fee (st.dev. 1.57). Payoffs in the two treatments were virtually identical.

3.2.2 Results

In this section we present descriptive statistics of participants' aggregate choice and revision patterns over time for the two treatments. Individual-level estimations of choice and time patterns is performed with a structural model in Section 4.

A majority of subjects adopted strategies involving revisions, and most of them transitioned from a first, fast and intuitive reply to more reflective choices. This was more pronounced in the Graphical treatment, where the first click is faster and the second slower than in Numeric. Subjects clicked only once on a screen less than a third of the time (28.1% Graphical, 30.6% Numeric). The first clicks happens on average after about 5 seconds (5.28 Numeric, 4.26 Graphical), and the second clicks four seconds later, after about 9 seconds (8.77 Numeric, 9.44 Graphical).

Figure 4: Choice shares and difference in time, for the first click only and for all clicks, by treatment

Figure 4 shows the choice shares of target, competitor and decoy in time. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals and are calculated over the means of individual shares. The dashed lines represent the time pattern of choices when considering *the first click only* (error bars omitted for clarity). The solid lines take into account all clicks, i.e., include revisions. The lower panel shows our measure of the attraction effect, the difference between the choice share of the target and the competitor. The attraction effect follows a rise-and-fall pattern. It first rises, reaches a maximum at about 25% percentage points advantage for the target, to then gradually decrease and reach nearly zero by the end of the allotted time. This is due in part to more accurate participants taking their time to choose (the dashed lines stabilize at levels lower than the 25% peak), but mostly to choice revisions (the difference between the dashed and solid lines). The effect is slightly more pronounced in the Numeric treatment, where it subsides earlier, than in the Graphical treatment. Complete table data of the effect of first and second clicks on choice shares of options and response time are provided in Appendix C. This rise-and-fall pattern is robust to different ways of measuring the attraction effect, by exploiting control screens with no or not obvious decoys (see Appendix B). The rise-and-fall pattern is also apparent from the very first trials – subjects do not need training on several trials to stop displaying the attraction effect over the 20 seconds of the task.⁴

We check the robustness of this pattern depending on the relative price of the target and competitor (appendix A). We find that the effect is present in all cases except in the case of indifference. This is because the fall in the relative share of the target is driven by revisions, which more closely approximate the objective difference in price between the target and the competitor. This driver does not operate

⁴For the Numeric treatment, Figure 4 shows a double-dip pattern, whereby the attraction effect drops to zero at around 10 seconds, to then rise and fall again. This pattern is not replicated at different levels of relative prices (see Figure A.1 in appendix A), nor when applying alternative measures of the attraction effect (see appendix B). We hence do not venture interpreting it.

when the target and the competitor are actually indifferent.

3.3 Experiment 2

In Experiment 2 we aimed for four distinct goals: replicate the results of Experiment 1 on a larger sample of diverse consumers, specifically excluding students; adopt a more robust measure for the attraction effect, based on the work of Trueblood et al. (2014); optimize the stimuli and the choice screens to allow precise estimation of an MLBA model with revisions; and extend the analysis to the compromise and similarity effects. The cover story, the task, and the elicitation method were the same as the Graphical treatment of Experiment 1.

3.3.1 Methods

Stimuli and measure

In Experiment 2 we used redesigned graphical stimuli to improve the ability to discern between offers. With respect to the stimuli of the Graphical treatment of Experiment 1, we changed color to provide better contrast with the background, added a relative, empty-full scale on the side to improve the comparability of offers, and used simple bars to show the size of the gas tank. Figure 5 shows an offer in Experiment 2.

Figure 5: Stimuli used in Experiment 2

The choice screens were chosen in order to implement the measure of context effects used by Trueblood et al. (2014). Figure 6 (a) provides a graphical description of the stimuli for the case of the AE, and indifference between the target and the competitor. Starting from two indifferent options A and B, we create the two choice sets ABC and ABD, with C being a decoy for A and D being a decoy for B. With reference to Figure 6 (a), the measure of the attraction effect is given by

$$\text{effect} = \left(\frac{\bar{A}_{ABC} - \bar{B}_{ABC}}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{\bar{B}_{ABD} - \bar{A}_{ABD}}{2} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{\bar{A}_{ABC} - \bar{A}_{ABD}}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{\bar{B}_{ABD} - \bar{B}_{ABC}}{2} \right)$$

where \bar{A}_{ABC} is the choice share of option A in choice set ABC. This measure distills the best features of the main and control measures of Experiment 1 into one unique measure.

The simple difference between the target and competitor is computed twice, in order to clear the impact of a particular option on the measure and to average over size and price decoys. As can easily be seen by the two identical formulations of the measure, the measure is equivalent to taking the average of the main measure of Experiment 1 (target - competitor) across the two choice sets (leftmost definition), but also to taking the average of the control measure of Experiment 1 (target in presence

Figure 6: Design and measures for Experiment 2

The vertical axis is $\hat{q}_i = \ln(q_i)$ and the horizontal axis is $\hat{p}_i = -\ln(p_i)$. Indifference lines $U = \ln(q_i) - \ln(p_i)$ thus corresponds to all options such that $q/p = e^U$.

vs. absence of a decoy) but in a symmetric way whereby the target takes the role of competitor and vice-versa (rightmost definition).

The measure can be readily extended to a situation of different relative prices between the target and the competitor. In Figure 6 (b), we can apply the above measure to the choice sets $AB'C$ and $A'BD$ to get a clean measure of the attraction effect, whereby each option enjoys a better or worse price, and plays the role of competitor and target. In this case, we compute

$$\text{effect} = \left(\frac{\bar{A}_{AB'C} - \bar{B}'_{AB'C}}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{\bar{B}_{A'BD} - \bar{A}'_{A'BD}}{2} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{\bar{A}_{AB'C} - \bar{A}'_{A'BD}}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{\bar{B}_{A'BD} - \bar{B}'_{AB'C}}{2} \right)$$

The similarity and compromise effects are measured in exactly the same way – all that changes is the position of the decoys. In both cases decoys belong to the same indifference line of the target and competitor. In the case of Similarity, the decoy is very close to the competitor, and its presence is meant to make the dissimilar option – the target – stand out (Figure 6 (c).) In the case of compromise, the decoys are located in such a way that the target becomes the “middle” option, i.e. is located exactly in the center of the line connecting the decoy and the competitor (Figure 6 (d)). Both effects are also analyzed when varying relative prices, with the same mechanism shown for the Attraction effect in Figure 6 (b).

Experimental details and procedures

We ran 9 experimental sessions involving a total of 198 participants. The sessions took place in Grenoble, France, in September 2021. Participants were recruited from the same subject pool as Experiment 1, but excluding students. No person having participated in Experiment 1 was allowed to participate in Experiment 2. The sample was made nearly entirely of consumers, working (69%) or unemployed/retired (28%), with only 4% of students – against 53% of students for Experiment 1. Experiment 2 subjects were on average older, with higher revenue, slightly less educated, and scored lower on the CRT. Details of the demographics of the sample are reported in Table E.1 in Appendix E.

The procedures were kept as similar as possible to Experiment 1. With respect to Experiment 1, we improved the instructions, added control questions in-between instructions and the training phase, and made two smaller training phases instead of a single, larger one. All these changes were done to increase comprehension of the instructions and the elicitation mechanism. All other details were the same.

Subjects faced 42 screens, in individually drawn random order. They were constructed as explain

in appendix M.2. It took about 20 minutes to cycle through all the decision screens. After the main task, subjects answered to three questionnaires (down from six for Experiment 1). We kept the socio-demographic, risk attitude and CRT questionnaires, as the comprehension, trust, and shopping questionnaire had no impact on our results for Experiment 1.

The English translation of the original French instructions is in Appendix L. The web-based experimental software (same as Experiment 1) as well as the original French instructions are available upon request. Participants received a 10€ show-up fee. Eight randomly picked screens out of the 42 were individually and independently drawn to be payoff relevant. Subjects earned on average 10.6€ in addition to the show-up fee.

3.3.2 Results

As for Experiment 1, here we present descriptive statistics for the aggregate patterns of first choices and revisions; for individual-level estimations and structural modeling see Section 4.

A majority of subjects revised their choice for all effects. Subjects clicked only once on a screen less than half the time for all effects (49.1% attraction, 42.5% similarity, 39.8% compromise). This lower number of revisions, especially for the AE, is possibly due to the cleaner stimuli allowing to more easily spot the decoy. The average time of first choices and successive revisions is also similar to Experiment 1, albeit slower across the board. First clicks happened on average after 5.75 seconds for the Attraction effect (4.26 seconds in the comparable Graphical treatment of Experiment 1), 6.29 for similarity and 6.94 for compromise. Attraction is faster as subjects perceive the dominated decoy and choose in order to avoid being allocated the decoy in case of delayed first choice; but not as fast as in Experiment 1, possibly due to the presence of the scale giving incentives to subjects to be precise. Second clicks take about 4 seconds more, and happen on average at 9.37 seconds for attraction, 10.3 seconds for similarity and 11.8 seconds for compromise.

Figure 7 shows the choice shares of target, competitor and decoy in time for each effect (top) and the measure of the effect in time (bottom), for the first click (dashed) and all clicks (solid line). Reference lines indicate the choice shares that should prevail absent any context effect. This is 50% for the Attraction effect, since the decoy is dominated and should never be chosen; and 33% for the other effects, since in this case all options, including the decoy, sit on the same indifference line.

We closely replicate the attraction effect results of Experiment 1, with a clear rise-and-fall pattern, largely but not only driven by revisions. Differently from Experiment 1, the effect does not completely disappear, but stays significantly different from zero until the very end. This might be due to the different demographic composition of the sample, made up of older, slightly less educated subjects and with virtually no university student (see Table E.1 in Appendix E).

The same rise-and-fall pattern is observed for the similarity effect, but at a much lower intensity and with a much shorter duration. The effect is limited to the first two and a half seconds, where only 10% (at one second) at 30% (at two seconds) of subjects have made a choice; it is hence a limited and ephemeral effect that is shown by the subpopulation of very fast first clickers. The effect settles to a very slightly reverse similarity effect towards the end of the allotted time.

Unexpectedly, we fail to replicate the compromise effect. Our data rather highlights a *reverse compromise* effect, whereby the most extreme option – the decoy – is the most chosen one. Since in compromise screens, the decoy usually displays a very large quantity for a very small price, or vice-versa, this might have made it easier for subjects to compute the implicit unit price for that option, since one dimension can be nearly disregarded. In the remainder of this section we report the results for the reverse compromise effect that we found. This is done by considering as target the option that was most extreme in either price or quantity, and considering the middle option as the decoy – i.e. the option

Figure 7: Choice shares and difference in time, for the first click only and for all clicks, by effect

not frequently chosen, whose existence makes the extreme option stand out. Figure 7, rightmost panel, is drawn by applying these different roles to the options. Using Figure 6, d for reference, we consider, within choice set ABC, C to be the target, B the competitor, and A the decoy. This reverse compromise effect has been found elsewhere in the literature (for instance in their by-alternative elicitation by [Cataldo and Cohen, 2019](#)), and it *also* follows a rise-and-fall pattern, not disappearing by the end of the allotted time – as in the case of the surviving AE in Experiment 1, this might be driven by indifference among options. As in experiment 1, the pattern is robust to different relative prices of the target vs. the competitor (Appendix D).

Overall, context effects in our experiment seem to generally follow a rise-and-fall pattern; but our stimuli do not always identify the effect we expected. As in Experiment 1, there is no role for learning across trials in our data; the rise-and-fall pattern is already established on the very first choice screens.

4 A Multi-Attribute Linear Ballistic Accumator Model with Choice Revisions (MLBA-R)

We looked for a model that could account for both the speed and biases in choice, but was simple enough to be extended to take account of choice revisions. We chose to model *decision times* by using the Linear Ballistic Accumulation model ([Brown and Heathcote, 2008](#)). This model is attractive because it has analytic solutions and thus a likelihood function, allowing us to adapt standard estimation tools for its estimation. We elected to model *context effects* using the MLBA extension of the LBA model in [Trueblood et al. \(2014\)](#), as refined in [Evans et al. \(2019\)](#). This model can explain different types of context effects with a relatively low number of parameters that can be interpreted in intuitive ways. We simplified the LBA model into a *dynamic version of a Luce model of individual choice behavior* ([Luce, 2012](#)), as explained in [Colonius and Marley \(2015\)](#). This allows us to go on to estimate our more complicated version of the LBA that allows for choice revisions. We estimate that model based on the methods outlined in [Annis et al. \(2017\)](#) for Bayesian estimation with Stan ([Stan Development Team, 2021](#)).

Overall, the MLBA model compares well with alternatives, such as the Multi-attribute Leaky Competing Accumulator model (MLCA, Usher and McClelland, 2004), the Multi-alternative Decision Field Theory (MDFT, Roe et al., 2001b), the Association and Accumulation Model (AAM, Bhatia, 2013) or the Multialternative Decision by Sampling (MDbS, Noguchi and Stewart, 2018). Indeed, Evans et al. (2019) show that while all those model do a good job at predicting response times in context effect experiments, the MLBA outperforms them in predicting choice shares (Figures 4 and 5). Cataldo and Cohen (2020) find the same (Figures 6 and 7). They underline however that the MLBA is not very flexible in predicting variations in the share of different options as a function of decision times. It therefore does not allow to reflect their finding that, within individual, speed of decision influences the size of the context effects, whereas the MDFT appears to be better at reflecting this (Figure 8). Moreover, Molloy et al. (2019) underline the importance of including response times in inferences using the MLBA. Our extension of the MLBA takes account of the possibility to revise choices and thus allows a richer pattern of rise and fall in context effects over time.

Our modeling fulfills several different aims. A first aim is to separate different factors in the decisions of individuals, namely the speed of their decisions, their precision, how biased they are by the context, and their willingness to revise choices. Following on this contribution, we are able to make a typology of decision makers, whereby some choose fast but in a biased way, while others choose slowly and are less biased. We extend this typology by also noticing that some of those who choose fast are also more flexible in their choice, meaning they are willing to revise their choice after further consideration. Finally, we show that our model generalizes well to explain different patterns of choices and revisions over time under different contexts (dominance, similarity, compromise). It can explain a variety of patterns in the dynamics of choice without requiring the introduction of additional, *ad-hoc* parameters.

In our model's "mechanical" explanation of the dynamics of choice, decision-makers do not only make a choice among options, but also perform choice editing, whereby they eliminate options from the consideration set and then concentrate on the remaining options. This process of choice editing is also influenced by the context, and results in changing the context of the decision. In our case, bias is reduced after choice editing, since only two options then remain. Choice revisions therefore tend to reduce the contextual bias displayed in first choices. We show that our model generalizes well to contexts where choice editing is not as straightforward as under the attraction effect.

Overall, the main contribution of the model is to allow us to distinguish the process of choice editing from the influence of the context, and to show how the two combine to give a satisfactory account of our observations. We underline the importance of the willingness to revise choices as a psychological factor that explains why and how context effects may decline when given enough time to reconsider past decisions.

In the following, we first present in section 4.1 the model in three steps, first the LBA back-end dealing with decision times, then our extension of this back-end to allow for revisions, and finally the MLBA front-end which accounts for biases in favor or against options in a choice set depending on their context. We provide simulations to clearly link the model with the experimental findings. Then we provide model estimates (4.2), explore individual differences (4.3) and produce post-estimation predictions (K.1).

4.1 The MLBA-R – a model of choice revisions over time

4.1.1 The MLBA back-end: modeling decision times

We use a simplified version of the original LBA model, where accumulation of evidence starts from different point for each option, and drifts are drawn from a Normal distribution. Following Colonius and Marley (2015), we assume no starting point variability in the accumulator z_{it} , and multiplicative draw

of drifts from a Fréchet distribution. Indeed, maintaining the original version would require numerical integration to estimate the likelihood in the more complex model with revisions we present next. This is feasible and we programmed it, but it is computationally costly and thus prohibitively slow with current software and computing capacity.

An option is chosen if it is the first to accumulate a level of evidence $\chi > 0$ in a race between options over time. Formally, denote $d = (d_i, d_j, d_k)$ a vector of the mean drift of options i, j, k . Those are constrained to be positive. The accumulator (or evidence) for option i at time t is $z_{it} = \tilde{d}_i(t - \tau)$. We let $\tilde{d}_i = d_i \tilde{r}$, with \tilde{r} following a Fréchet distribution (a.k.a. inverse Weibull), that is, $F(r) = e^{-r^{-\alpha}}$ for $r > 0$, 0 else, with $\alpha > 0$. τ is the consideration time, that is, the time needed before evidences accumulate.⁵ Option i is chosen if it is the first to accumulate $z_{it} = \chi$. We denote T the maximum time for making a choice. If the accumulator at T is less than χ , then no choice is observed. Figure 8 shows graphically the (linear) trajectory that each option follows, whereby evidence is on the ordinate and time on the abscissa. The option with the highest slope is chosen at time $t = \frac{\chi}{d_i \tilde{r}}$. This is not always the option with the highest drift due to the random term \tilde{r} .

Figure 8: First choice, and revision process

In this example, option i is chosen at time t_1 . The set of options is reduced to i and second-best j for the revision. Choice is revised to option j at time t_2 .

At time t' , the accumulator for i will have reached level $z_{it} = d_i r t'$. This is higher than threshold χ at time t with probability $F_i(\chi, t) = p(z_{it} \geq \chi) = p(\frac{\chi}{d_i r} \leq t) = p(r \geq \frac{\chi}{d_i t}) = 1 - e^{-(\frac{d_i t}{\chi})^\alpha}$. Decision times thus follow an extreme value distribution, such that $f_i(\chi, t) = \alpha \frac{d_i}{\chi} (\frac{d_i t}{\chi})^{\alpha-1} e^{-(\frac{d_i t}{\chi})^\alpha}$. That is, $f_i(\chi, t)$ follows a Weibull distribution with shape α and scale $\beta = \chi/d_i$. Option i will be chosen at time t with probability

$$\begin{aligned} f_i(t) &= p(t_i = t \cap t_j > t \cap t_k > t) \\ &= f_i(\chi, t)(1 - F_j(\chi, t))(1 - F_k(\chi, t)) \\ &= \alpha \frac{d_i}{\chi} \left(\frac{d_i t}{\chi}\right)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\sum (\frac{d_i t}{\chi})^\alpha} \end{aligned}$$

The cumulative distribution function of that event is $F_i(t) = \frac{d_i^\alpha}{\sum d_i^\alpha} (1 - e^{-(\frac{t}{\chi})^\alpha \sum d_i^\alpha})$. This means that for any decision time t , the probability that option i is the option chosen is $p_i = \frac{d_i^\alpha}{\sum d_i^\alpha}$ and the time at which

⁵In the following, to simplify the writing, we take as a given that τ has already been subtracted from times t . We reintroduce τ later on in the simulations; this parameter allows us to take account of very rapid, random choices that occur in early stages of the choice timeline.

an option is chosen is distributed according to c.d.f. $F(t) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\chi}\right)^\alpha \Sigma d_i^\alpha}$. This time distribution is independent of which specific option is under consideration.

Our model implies that the share of each option in terms of first choice does not vary with time. This characteristic will allow us to separate dynamics due to first choice (which are non-existent in our model) and dynamics due to revisions in second choices. All dynamics we obtain theoretically can therefore only be due to revisions. We checked that our simplification was also justified empirically. This is the case as we do not observe changes in shares of first choices among options in our tasks at the individual level in our data. Note that this does not exclude some aggregate dynamics in first choices given individual differences in biases and speed of choices. We will underline those differences in the analysis of the results of our regressions.

4.1.2 Extending the MLBA to take account of choice revisions

We extend the MLBA to account for the possibility to revise choices. We call this the MLBA-R, that is, a MLBA model with revisions. We assume that once the first option to reach threshold χ is chosen at time t_1 , a new race is started between that option and the second best option at that time, that is, the option with the second highest level of evidence in its favor at time t_1 . If for example option i reaches χ at time t_1 and is the first to do so, then the second best option is $j = \arg \max_{l \neq i} z_{lt_1}$. We illustrate this in figure 8 where option k is eliminated from the consideration set when starting a second race between i and j .

The second best option thus enters a second race with i , whereby drifts are computed and drawn again given the new context with only two options. In this second race, we allow for a possible tendency to either *stay* with the first option or switch to another option by multiplying the drift of the first option chosen by *stay* (see page 19 in section 4.1.3). If i wins again, or no option reaches threshold χ before the time limit T , then the choice of i is maintained. If j wins at time t_2 and $t_2 < T$, the time limit, then the choice is revised to j . More details on the probability calculations to compute the log-likelihood of our model are presented in Appendix F.

4.1.3 The MLBA front-end: modeling context effects

The main innovation in Trueblood et al. (2014) is a model to generate the “drifts” d , that is, the average speed at which evidence accumulates for an option in the LBA model. This is what they call a “front-end” extension of the linear ballistic accumulator model. We adopt a further refinement including an additional parameter γ as in Evans et al. (2019).

We explain here how we derive drifts d from a set of options i, j, k characterized by the vector $((x_{1i}, x_{2i}), (x_{1j}, x_{2j}), (x_{1k}, x_{2k}))$, whereby the objective value of an option i is $v_i = x_{1i} + x_{2i}$.⁶

A *first step* obtains (u_{1i}, u_{2i}) such that

$$u_{1i} = \frac{(x_{1i} + x_{2i})}{(1 + (x_{2i}/x_{1i})^m)^{1/m}} \text{ and } u_{2i} = \frac{(x_{1i} + x_{2i})}{(1 + (x_{1i}/x_{2i})^m)^{1/m}}.$$

Parameter m translates extremeness aversion. $m > 1$ results in aversion to extreme options, that is, to options where most of the value comes from one dimension only.⁷ If $m = 1$, then $(u_{1i}, u_{2i}) = (x_{1i}, x_{2i})$. If $m < 1$, then we obtain a preference for extreme options.

⁶In our experiment, the ratio quantity over price q/p is what must be maximized. This can be translated into $\ln q - \ln p$. We then characterize each option so $x_{1i} = \hat{p}_i = \ln(p_{max}) - \ln(p_i)$ and $x_{2i} = \hat{q}_i = \ln(q_i) - \ln(q_{min})$, whereby (p_{max}, q_{min}) correspond to the highest possible shown price among the tasks and q_{min} the lowest possible quantity among the tasks. The value of option i is then $v_i = x_{1i} + x_{2i} = \hat{p}_i + \hat{q}_i = \ln(p_{max}) - \ln(p_i) + \ln(q_i) - \ln(q_{min})$. The option with the highest value v is also the one with the highest ratio q/p . We chose p_{max} and q_{min} to correspond to maximum and minimum values of those parameters in the experiment, but acknowledge that those reference values may vary over time as participants learn from options shown to them.

⁷e.g. an option with values (4,6) on dimensions 1 and 2 respectively is not as good as an option with values (5,5), even if their objective value is the sum of both dimensions.

A *second step* obtains weights (attention) given to the comparison of options i and j on dimension n . Those depend on the absolute value of the difference in the value of options, such that options that are close to each other on one dimension attract more attention. We have

$$\begin{aligned}w_{1ij} &= \exp(-\lambda|u_{1i} - u_{1j}|) \\w_{2ij} &= \exp(-\beta\lambda|u_{2i} - u_{2j}|)\end{aligned}$$

This value function translates how people go about pair comparisons on single dimensions, whereby values that are closer attract more attention, as shown in [Noguchi and Stewart \(2014\)](#).⁸ Parameter β may differ from 1 to allow for a difference in how individuals go about comparisons across the two dimensions.

A *third step* obtains the V matrix of binary comparisons, with elements

$$V_{ij} = w_{1ij}(u_{1i} - u_{1j}) + w_{2ij}(u_{2i} - u_{2j}).$$

In a *final step*, elements of this matrix are combined to obtain the vector of drifts for each options, $d = (d_i, d_j, d_k)$, whereby

$$d_i = I_0 + \gamma \sum_{j \neq i} V_{ij}$$

This function suggests that options are compared in pairs rather than globally. Drifts are restricted to be greater than 0.

Calculation of drifts in the second race The same calculations can be made when comparing only two options with each other. In our model, this happens when revisions are being made, as this involves a comparison between only the first and second runner in the first race between options.

We introduce parameter *stay* to the model to translate a possible advantage or disadvantage to the first option chosen when the second race is run. This parameter makes psychological sense, as revising one's choice requires effort and also accepting that one's first choice was not optimal. This parameter also introduces memory of past choices in the choice process. A value *stay* > 1 means there is a tendency to stay with the first option chosen.⁹ Denoting $d' = (d'_i, d'_j)$ whereby i is the option first chosen and j is the second best, we thus let¹⁰

$$d'_i = (I_0 + 2\gamma V_{ij}) \times \textit{stay} \text{ and } d'_j = I_0 + 2\gamma V_{ji}.$$

We summarize our parameters in [Table 1](#).

⁸Unlike in [Trueblood et al., 2014](#), we do not let λ differ depending on whether $u_{ni} - u_{nj}$ is positive (λ^+) or negative (λ^-) because we did not find significant differences between those two parameters.

⁹We note that *stay* < 1 can lead to a reversal in contextual effects over time, whereby the early favored option is disproportionately disfavored later on. This could happen if for example some participants overestimate the extent to which bias affected their first choice.

¹⁰Note how γ is multiplied by two here so as to be consistent with γ when there are three options. Alternatively, one could also have written $d_i = I_0 + \gamma \sum_{j \neq i} \frac{V_{ij}}{2}$ when there are three options and $d_i = I_0 + \gamma V_{ij}$ when there are two options, so that speed depends on the average difference in value with other options rather than their sum.

Parameter	Description	Allowable range
I_0	Baseline input	$I_0 \geq 0$
γ	Choice accuracy	$\gamma \geq 0$
m	Exponent transforming objective to subjective values	$m > 0$
$\lambda, \beta\lambda$	Decay constant for attention weights, dimensions 1 and 2	$\lambda, \beta \geq 0$
$stay$	Tendency to stay with the first option chosen	$stay \in \mathbb{R}$
α	Shape of the time distribution	$\alpha > 0$
χ	Threshold amount of evidence required to trigger a choice	Fixed, $\chi = 1$
τ	Consideration time	Fixed, $\tau = \min(t)$

Table 1: Parameters and Allowable Ranges for the Multi-attribute Linear Ballistic Accumulator Model with Revisions

Interpretation of parameters I_0 translates randomness in choice, as this is the part of the drifts that does not vary across options, while γ translates accuracy in choice, that is, how far the difference V_{ij} in weighted values between options influences choice. Higher I_0 and γ mean that choice will be made more quickly, and a higher I_0 relative to γ means that choices will be made more randomly. The mean speed of choice also varies with α whereby an option with drift d facing an option with 0 drift will be chosen at time $\chi\Gamma(1+1/\alpha)/d$ on average, whereby Γ is the Gamma function, with special cases $\Gamma(n) = (n-1)!$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

V_{ij} are computed with the parameters λ, m and β , whereby parameters λ and m do most of the work in accounting for the attraction, similarity and compromise effects. Higher λ results in larger differences in the attention given to options that are close together rather than farther away. In the case of the attraction effect, then this draws relatively higher attention to the pair target-decoy because they are close together. Since the target is superior to the decoy, then this attention comes at the expense of the decoy and benefits the target vs. the competitor. In the case of the similarity effect, then the pair that is close together also draws attention, but this attention is split between the two options since they are similar in value, so this benefits the third, far away option. In the case of the compromise effect, then this parameter is not so important since all options are similarly far from each other. In this later case however, parameter m comes into play: the more there is aversion to extreme options ($m > 1$), the more the middle option will be favored. Conversely, if $m < 1$, then extreme options will be preferred.

A special case that corresponds to rational fully informed choice, whereby an individual considers only the sum of the dimensions for each option, $v_i = x_{1i} + x_{2i}$. This is so if $m = 1$ and $\lambda = 0$. Then drifts for each of three options is simply $d_i = I_0 + \gamma \times ((v_i - v_j) + (v_i - v_k))$, whereby what matters is simply a comparison of the objective value of each option with respect to the alternatives.

Parameter β translates how differences on one dimension matter compared with differences on the other. For example, $\beta < 1$ if consumers pay more attention to differences in the second dimension, maybe because it is shown first in the lexicographical order when presenting options, or because it is shown in a more intuitive way, such as with a figure.

4.1.4 Simulations

In order to illustrate the working of our model, we simulate decision times and choice shares for representative choice set comparisons, following the model of exposition in Trueblood et al. (2014). Table G.1 in Appendix G shows artificial stimuli for the simulations, whereby the objective value of an option is the sum of its two components. The target is the option that is chosen more often if the effect holds. Two choice sets are presented for each effect, so as to keep two options the same and only vary the third, decoy option. The magnitude of the context effect is the average choice share of the target across

Option	First choice share %	time	Option	Revision share %	time	Option	After revision share %
Target	54%	(6.92)	Competitor	32%	(6.88)	Target	52%
			Decoy	0%	(-)		
			No revision	68%	(-)		
Competitor	42%	(6.81)	Target	28%	(6.76)	Competitor	47%
			Decoy	1%	(8.18)		
			No revision	71%			
Decoy	4%	(1)	Target	87%	(7.74)	Decoy	1%
			Competitor	0%	(-)		
			No revision	13%			

Table 2: Simulated first choices, revisions, and final choice, for the attraction effect

the two choice sets. This measure neutralizes the effect of differences between target and competitor other than the context in which they are presented.

We simulate choices using our model and parameters consistent with our subsequent estimates: $I_0 = 1$, $\gamma = 3$, $m = 2$, $\lambda = 0.5$, $\beta = 1$, $stay = 1$, $\alpha = 1$, $\chi = 1$, $\tau = 0.1$. We show resulting frequency of choices and revision patterns in Table 2 for the attraction effect, along with average choice speed.

With those parameters, the target in choice sets with attraction effect is chosen 54% of the time as a first choice. The decoy is chosen 3% of the time, mainly as a random choice within the first two seconds of choice ($\tau = 0.1$). This explains why choices of the target are made so fast. Revisions lead the share of the target back to 52%. This is because 32% of the original choice of the target are revised to the competitor, and 28% of the choices of the competitor are revised to the target, which tends to equalize shares.¹¹ We also see that choices of the decoy are revised to the target rather than to the competitor, and otherwise are maintained. There is no choice made at all in about 6% of cases.

The same tables for the similarity and compromise effect are shown in Appendix H. We obtain a slight anti-similarity effect in first choices, whereby the similar competitor is chosen 36% of the time vs. 34% for the target. There is no rebalancing after revisions. There is a compromise effect, whereby 55% of the first choices are for the compromise option. A rebalancing occurs after second choices, whereby the share of the target is revised down to 52%.

We see from those examples that if there are context effects in first choices, then they tend to be reduced after revisions are made.

Figure 9 shows the evolution of the share of each option for each effect, as a proportion of choices made. We see there that the share of each option early on is 33%, as choices made before the minimum consideration time τ are made at random. The consideration time τ reflects the empirical distribution of decision times, whereby a small proportion of choices are made very rapidly, with every option getting similar shares. Choice proportions then evolve as considered choices are made, climbing to their share of first choices as shown in Table 2.

Shares then adjust as revisions take account of other factors. For example, the share of the target and of the competitor converge in attraction choice sets. Convergence is not fully to 50% because of the time limit, so not all have time to revise their choices. There is no convergence in similarity choice sets, and convergence as under the attraction effect in compromise choice sets. Dotted lines on the graph show the share of options if only first choices were taken into account, in order to visualize the difference due to revisions.

The main lesson from those graphs is that we obtain non-monotonous patterns in the share of

¹¹Given the time limit T , not all deciders are fast enough to have the time to make a second choice, so the choice shares does not fully converge to 50% each.

Figure 9: Simulated proportions of choices made over time

options if we include patterns of revisions in our model.¹² This is because first choices, which tend to occur early compared to second choices, favor one option because they consider all options, and thus the context. Revisions on the other hand involve comparisons between pairs of options, i.e. without the influence of a third option, so the effect of the context converges downward.¹³

4.2 Model parameter estimates

We estimate parameters in the model using Bayesian methods. We estimate a “basic” MLBA model that takes only first choices into account. We then estimate our extended MLBA-R model that includes choice revisions. We finally estimate a mixed-effects model (a.k.a. in the literature as random-effects, multilevel or hierarchical model). This allows parameters to vary by individual so we obtain “regularized” mean estimates of the parameters and of their variability across individuals. The resulting estimates are more useful for broader inferences as they are independent of the particular individuals in our sample. We also obtain “regularized” estimates of the parameters for each individual. Those are more reliable than estimates we would obtain from independently estimating parameters for each individual. Indeed, those regularized estimates take account not only of the data for an individual, but also of information gained from estimates for other individuals. In mathematical terms, we let $p \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_p, \tau_p)$ for parameter $p \in \{I, \gamma, m, \lambda, \beta, stay\}$ and thus obtain estimates not only of μ_p , the mean of p , but also of τ_p , the standard deviation of p across individuals. Details on our estimation procedure are given in Appendix I.

Table 3 shows results of our estimation of parameters for the model with mixed effects. We split results in Experiment 1 by whether stimuli sizes were shown graphically or numerically (see Figure 1). We estimate all effects together in Experiment 2 rather than splitting estimates by effect, based on the (verified) principle that our model of choice applies to all contexts, and parameters therefore ought not to depend on the context under consideration. Appendix J, table J.1 shows results for the simpler models.

Parameter estimates in the mixed model are consistent with those of the other models, and differences across treatments are reduced. This makes sense since those are regularized estimates that abstract from individual variations to retrieve latent parameters. We also provide summary statistics for individual parameter estimates across individuals (Table J.2 and Figure J.1 in Appendix J).

The Graphical treatment of Experiment 1 and Experiment 2 obtain very similar regularized parameter estimates and average individual parameter estimates. This is because the presentation of options was similar in both. The only differences across treatments relate to the numeric treatment of Experiment

¹²Remember those changes in shares can only be due to revisions, as we simplified the model so that shares would stay the same over time if there were no revisions (see page 18)

¹³Note that revisions themselves still depend on how extreme an option is vs. another, for example. They therefore also reflect a bias, but that bias is not due to the original context effect.

Parameters	Exp 1: Graphical		Exp 1: Numeric		Exp 2	
	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI
μ_I	2.30	[2.11;2.50]	2.01	[1.69;2.37]	1.84	[1.70;1.99]
μ_γ	3.83	[3.52;4.15]	3.83	[3.51;4.16]	3.14	[2.82;3.47]
μ_m	0.97	[0.94;1.01]	1.00	[0.96;1.04]	0.92	[0.89;0.95]
μ_λ	0.15	[0.04;0.36]	0.09	[0.03;0.21]	0.08	[0.02;0.20]
μ_β	0.72	[0.65;0.80]	1.14	[1.07;1.21]	0.71	[0.67;0.76]
μ_{stay}	0.90	[0.79;1.02]	0.85	[0.78;0.92]	0.92	[0.82;1.03]
τ_I	0.89	[0.75;1.04]	1.29	[1.03;1.59]	1.08	[0.97;1.21]
τ_γ	1.39	[1.18;1.64]	1.32	[1.09;1.57]	1.68	[1.50;1.87]
τ_m	0.16	[0.13;0.18]	0.16	[0.14;0.20]	0.20	[0.17;0.22]
τ_λ	0.65	[0.54;0.76]	0.30	[0.24;0.37]	0.52	[0.46;0.57]
τ_β	0.31	[0.25;0.37]	0.26	[0.21;0.31]	0.25	[0.22;0.28]
τ_{stay}	0.64	[0.52;0.77]	0.32	[0.26;0.38]	0.82	[0.73;0.92]
α	1.76	[1.72;1.81]	1.80	[1.74;1.86]	1.97	[1.95;1.99]
LL	-700	[-742;-664]	-513	[-549;-483]	-6637	[-6756;-6527]
N		63		48		198
$Tasks$		20		20		36

Table 3: Parameter estimates, model with mixed effects

1, where estimates of μ_β are higher than 1 while they are lower than 1 in other treatments, and where estimates of $stay$ are lower than 1, while they are not significantly different from 1 in other treatments. We also find that parameter m is less than 1 in Experiment 2, while not being significantly different from 1 in other treatments.

Parameter λ is significantly more than 0 in all treatments, meaning that participants were more attentive to options that were close together. This explains how, in choice sets with similarity, options that were similar were more likely to be chosen than the dissimilar “target” option.¹⁴

Parameter β is significantly lower than 1 in the Graphical treatment of Experiment 1 and in Experiment 2, meaning that quantity differences were more important in the comparison process than price differences. This can be related to how quantities were more salient than prices in the graphical treatments, as they were shown graphically. Conversely, β was higher than 1 in the Numeric treatment, indicating that price differences were given more attention than quantity differences in the valuation of options. This can be related to how quantities were presented in the same way (numerically) as prices in that treatment, and price possibly being more focal.

Finally, participants were keen to switch from their first choice in the Numeric treatment ($\mu_{stay} < 1$), possibly because the presentation of options was more complex, requiring the processing of many numbers. This may have made the first, more intuitive choice, more difficult, thus lowering confidence in it. The $stay$ parameters were not significantly different from 0 in other treatments.

As noted, estimates of m were lower in Experiment 2 than in Experiment 1. There was no aversion or preference for extreme options in Experiment 1 ($m \simeq 1$), while there was a preference for extreme options in Experiment 2 ($m < 1$). This is consistent with the *reverse* compromise effect we observe in Experiment 2.

Post estimation results are shown in appendix K where we consider choice shares and revision

¹⁴The standard similarity effect is such that introduction of a similar “decoy” option lowers the share of the other similar “competitor” option, so the share of each similar options is lower than that of the dissimilar “target” option (although the sum of their shares may still be higher). In our experiment, the similarity effect is so strong that this more than compensates for the splitting of attention across both similar options, and the dissimilar “target” options ends up being chosen less often than either similar options.

dynamics implied by our model and estimated parameters. The model translates empirical observations from a qualitative point of view (rise and fall of the attraction effect, revisions away from the target). However, we do not replicate the magnitude of the effects; for example, post-estimates of the attraction effect are lower than observed in the data.

4.3 Individual differences

We further assess differences across individuals by splitting individual parameter estimates obtained in the mixed effects model into three component indicators based on the drift d_i of an option i in a choice set. From our model

$$d_i = I_0 + \gamma f_i(m, \lambda, \beta)$$

whereby d_i measures how attractive an option i when compared to j and k in a choice set. We note that $s_i = d_i^\alpha / \sum_j d_j^\alpha$ is the share of option i in terms of first choices in our model. Our first indicator is *speed* = $(I_0 + \gamma f') / \Gamma(1 + 1/\alpha)$, whereby we set $f' = 0.15$, the average difference in objective value between the target and decoy in our choice sets with attraction.¹⁵ The second indicator is *precision* = $d_T^\alpha / (d_T^\alpha + d_D^\alpha)$, the likelihood the target is chosen vs. the decoy is they are the only two options in a choice set, there are no biases ($\lambda = 0, m = 1$), and the value difference between the two is 0.15.¹⁶ This measures the relative contribution of chance in the choice of an option. Finally, the third indicator is *bias* = $sd(f_i, f_j, f_k)$ as the standard deviation of differences in values across options. This indicates how much the context affects choice across options.^{17,18} The advantage of using those indicators rather than parameter values is that there are fewer of them, and they allow to abstract from complex interactions between λ, β and m in determining bias for an option.

We show values of those indicators, averaged over individuals, in Table 4.¹⁹

Parameters	Exp 1: Graphical		Exp 1: Numeric		Exp 2	
	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI
Speed	3.27	[1.41;4.86]	3.13	[1.18;5.42]	2.77	[1.17;4.99]
Precision	0.73	[0.64;0.88]	0.76	[0.64;0.96]	0.75	[0.62;0.91]
Bias (attraction)	0.21	[0.17;0.27]	0.22	[0.18;0.25]	0.20	[0.16;0.25]
Bias (similarity)	0.06	[0.01;0.20]	0.02	[0.00;0.05]	0.05	[0.01;0.13]
Bias (compromise)	0.14	[0.03;0.41]	0.07	[0.02;0.11]	0.13	[0.05;0.27]
Stay	0.93	[0.41;1.89]	0.82	[0.49;1.12]	1.10	[0.40;2.02]
N	63		48		198	

Table 4: Speed, precision and bias, based on individual parameter estimates

We find that *speed* and *precision* are similar in Experiment 2 and in both treatments of Experiment 1. This is even though there was a wider array of different types of tasks (effects), and the possibility to make more precise comparison of quantities in Experiment 2.

Bias was also similar across different experiments. It is higher in choice sets with attraction than in

¹⁵ $\chi \Gamma(1 + 1/\alpha) / d$ is the average time at which an option with drift d is chosen in our model. The higher is speed, the lower is decision time.

¹⁶In this case, $d_T = I_0 + 0.15\gamma$ and $d_D = \max(I_0 - 0.15\gamma, 0)$.

¹⁷Remember that $\sum_i f_i = 0$ so we do not need to consider average levels of f .

¹⁸Note that *bias* = 0 if all options have the same unit price and choice is made on that basis only, i.e. if $m = 1, \lambda = 0$.

¹⁹We use choice sets in appendix G for comparability between Experiment 1 and 2. For each effect, we take average values when considering both a choice set with a decoy on quantity and its converse with a decoy on price, cf. design of choice sets in Experiment 2.

choice sets with similarity or compromise because options are equivalent in objective terms under those two effects, while the decoy is dominated in attraction tasks, so is seldom chosen.

Parameter *stay* was not significantly different from 1 in all experiments. This means that unlike what we would have expected, there was no status-quo effect, whereby participants are attached to their first choice. We will see in the analysis of correlation between those indicators that indeed, those who on average made the fastest first choices were the least likely to maintain it, that is, they switched more willingly than slower participants.

We move on to analyzing correlations between individual speed, precision and bias (Figures J.2 in appendix J). We find a negative relation between speed and precision in all treatments. There is a positive relation between speed and bias in the attraction effect for experiments 1 but not experiment 2. There is however a positive relation between speed and bias for other effects in Experiment 2. There is no consistent relation between precision and bias. Finally, parameter *stay* is negatively correlated with speed and positively correlated with precision, significantly so in Experiment 2. There is however no consistent relation between stay and bias for any of the effects in Experiment 2.

In other words, *individuals who make faster choices are generally less precise and more biased*. Furthermore, those who make fast choices are less likely to maintain those choices, while those who make more precise choices are more likely to maintain them.²⁰

5 Discussion

We study the choice process of individuals when faced with an objective-value choice task where context effects arise. Participants in our experiment are under constant time pressure and have the possibility to revise choices over time. We find that the attraction effect follows a rise-and-fall pattern over time. It is high in the first few seconds and then nearly disappears over a longer time span of 20 seconds. This rise-and-fall pattern is robust over two experiments with different samples, to using four different measures of the effect, and to differences in values between the target and the competitor. The AE sees no fall only in the special case of indifference among options, and this is further limited to Experiment 1, while in Experiment 2 the rise-and-fall pattern replicates to all cases.

This rise-and-fall pattern stems from two main sources: choice revisions, whereby subjects submit a first choice favoring the target and then move away from it when revising their choice; and subject heterogeneity, whereby some subjects submit fast choices using the AE as a heuristic, while others take their time and submit AE-free slower, more reflective choices. We further refine the typology of decision-makers by showing that many of the fast and biased individuals are willing to revise their biased first choices. They may be following an optimal strategy for choice under time constraint, whereby they use fast heuristics first and then switch to a more reflective mode if there is some time left.

We find that this rise-and-fall pattern is also present for other context effects, to the admittedly limited extent that those effects materialize in our experiments. We develop an original extension to the MLBA model of Trueblood et al. (2014) to include the possibility to revise decisions. Regularized model parameter estimates at the individual level confirm differences in the process of decision across individuals. This confirms the practical interest of using the MLBA model to study context effects.

Crucially, our results hold in an objective-value, induced-preference task where preferences do not differ across participants and there exist an objectively best option that can be identified through accurate measurement and computation. Within the limits imposed by our methodological choices, we can

²⁰ Allowing parameters of the model to differ depending on whether we consider first choices and second choice can allow us to refine this finding, whereby some individuals may make imprecise and biased fast first choices, and then precise unbiased slow second choices. Running regressions allowing for so many degrees of freedom is difficult however, but it is indeed the case that first choices are made faster on average than revisions to second choices.

unambiguously say that the attraction effect is mostly the result of a short-term heuristic, that is, for most subjects, superseded by more cognitively demanding processes after a few additional seconds; and we have some evidence that this rise-and-fall pattern holds for other context effects as well. On the other hand, the external validity of our findings depends on how well our experimental design translates into real-world choices, that are driven by preferences, where an objectively best option that can be reached by computation and introspection might not exist, and where there are opportunity cost to reconsidering a choice rather than moving on to other choices.

Rationalizing results from the literature If we take our results at face value, we can consider the attraction effect as a simple, fast decision strategy, akin to a heuristic. Doing so allows us to rationalize several disconnected results from the literature. The large list of settings in which the AE fails can be grouped in two different strands: settings in which other heuristics allow the participants to do better; and settings where the subject is incentivized to switch away from heuristic decision making and towards “slow”, “reflective” and “maximizing” strategies. Switch to competing heuristics more appropriate to the problem at hand can for instance explain why the AE is muted in presence of other focal cues (like brand, Ratneshwar et al., 1987), or when the product description is detailed and unambiguous (Mishra et al., 1993), or when the products are known and familiar to the consumer (Ratneshwar et al., 1987). Difficulty in recognizing and being relatively certain of dominance can explain the muting of the AE with pictorial representation of products (Frederick et al., 2014; Yang and Lynn, 2014) and in real-world choices (Trendl et al., 2021). Switching to “System 2”, slow decision modes can explain the disappearance of the effect when target and competitor differ in value (Crosetto and Gaudeul, 2016; Farmer et al., 2016). The interpretation of AE as a heuristic that is used if and until it is superseded by other processes is also supported by the fact that the AE survives *only* in conditions of indifference – i.e. when there is no need to move on to finer strategies – but at the same time it does appear, albeit temporarily, away from indifference, when, according to the very pioneers of the effect, *it should not* (Huber et al. (2014): “*when there are strong prior preferences, the classic model of choice will apply*”).

The view of the AE as a simple dominance-based heuristic is backed by several other existing results in the literature. Mao and Oppewal (2012) showed the AE to be more pronounced among consumers with an intuitive thinking style as measured by an abridged version of the Rational-Experiential Inventory questionnaire (Epstein et al., 1996). Pocheptsova et al. (2009) showed that the AE increases when participants’ cognitive resources were depleted (Masicampo and Baumeister, 2008) and when participants were tired. Hu and Yu (2014) showed in an fMRI study that the AE was associated with activation in areas of the brain linked with heuristics, and that those participants who had lower AE had activation in areas linked to cognitive control. Howes et al. (2016) showed that context effects, as heuristics in general, can be optimal when signals are noisy or decision makers are inaccurate in their assessment of options.

Ability and willingness to switch decision modes More generally, our findings show that participants can switch between decision modes when given incentives to do so. This point was made already in early literature on the topic (Payne et al., 1988, 1993), that argued that participants use phased decision strategies, whereby they employ different types of processing at different phases of the decision. Our experiment allows us to provide some clear, incentivized and measurable empirical evidence behind the use of such phased decision processes. Our findings also resonate with a very recent literature on the possibility to correct behavioral biases by confronting participants with their inconsistencies and offering them different ways to revise their submitted choices or state their confidence in them (Nielsen and Rehbeck, 2022; Benjamin et al., 2020; Enke and Graeber, 2019).

Our main finding of a rise-and-fall pattern for the AE does not directly contradict previous research that shows that less time pressure increases context effects (Pettibone, 2012; Trueblood et al., 2014; Dhar et al., 2000). Indeed, our task does not *force* participants into quick decisions, but puts them in a situation where they trade off speed and accuracy, and hence gives them *incentives* to reveal whether their dynamic answering strategy relies on using a fast heuristic and then revise their choice, or in just using the former, or in waiting till they can provide a refined, accurate answer. We indeed do replicate the fact that in the first few seconds the effect shoots up; however, unlike in other experiments which stop time after 2, 4, 5, 8 seconds and do not allow for revisions, we give more time and keep on observing. This allows participants to make slow choices if they wish to, and to revise their early fast choices. This results in the overall effect falling down to nearly zero in Experiment 1 — except in the special case of indifference between target and competitor — and to about a third of the peak in Experiment 2.

Are the findings externally valid? The peculiar task chosen for our study limits nonetheless the claims we can make with respect to the external validity of our findings. Our results might even support an opposite claim, i.e. vouch for the robustness of the attraction effect, since it manages to survive, albeit to a small extent and in situations of indifference, in a very hostile setting where we should not observe it. From this perspective our results show that given enough time, incentives, and in a context where using a reflective decision mode can make a difference, subjects move away from their intuitive first responses and towards behavior that can be described as consistent with rational choice principles. However, our results are silent on whether these conditions hold in real choice situations, and what the attraction effect pattern would look like in a more realistic setting involving preferences, weighing of fuzzily evaluated options in utility space, and where subjects face the opportunity cost of time and could hence move fast to other decisions (Imas et al., 2022). Most of the previous literature on the attraction effect never forced subjects to give a fast reply, implying that subjects autonomously chose to stop thinking and move on to the next task; to the extent that this is true in real choice situations, those might not exhibit the rise-and-fall pattern documented in this paper.

Are the findings relevant to other contexts? The extent to which our results will apply outside of our admittedly special setting is hence an open question, which can be addressed experimentally or empirically. We believe that in many settings, though, time, tools and incentives for subjects to revise and refine their choices *do* exist. They might learn to make first intuitive choices and then revise them, either by taking more parameters into account or by relying on advice from other consumers, on specialized information by experts, or on advice from friends and family. They may also simply do so because of the incentives involved when the amounts at stake increase. Documenting a rise-and-fall pattern, and a decrease in time of context effects when given incentives, in preference-based tasks and across a variety of conditions constitutes a much needed research program. This is nonetheless beyond the scope of our paper, whose aim is to document the pattern and provide evidence of its robustness.

It is also possible that our design creates artefactual incentives for participants to adopt a *fast then slow* heuristic. Indeed, our choice process elicitation mechanism gives an incentive for rational decision makers, who are aware of their cognitive limits, to provide a first, intuitive reply and to then revise it. If a rational decision maker could make a fast, accurate first reply she should do it. But if she knows that she needs time to provide an accurate choice, then it is in her best interest to submit a provisional choice in favor of a good-enough option before possibly revising her choice. Thus, the rise-and-fall pattern could be a direct consequence of our design, since it produces incentives to *both* overstate the early preference for the target, *and* to mobilize tools to revise one's choices.

We believe this artefactual effect to be a minor concern. First, it is unrelated to the external validity

of our findings, since in real choice situations consumers could use the exact same reasoning – provide an intuitive reply based on dominance in case of limited time and cognitive resources, think through the choice if time and incentives allow for it. This is in line with old and robust evidence that the attraction effect is mainly due to dominance (Wedell, 1991). Our design just allows us to observe both strategies, that in the real world might apply to different choices, on a single choice task, as if under a magnifying glass. Second, despite the incentive to be *fast then slow*, a sizable share of participants did *not* switch from fast heuristic to slow, accuracy-based choice: some preferred to wait and submit a later, more accurate choice, and others choose to follow only the fast heuristic and stop revisions. Subjects could and did follow their preferred choice path within our incentive scheme.

Summary and conclusion Our findings about the rise-and-fall pattern of the attraction effect help to make sense and generalize the debate in marketing on the existence and robustness of the AE, and provide a starting point from which to build experiments to assess the actual relevance of the effect in real choice situations.

We show that subjects do revise choices in the direction prescribed by rational choice theory in an objective-value task where an optimal choice is available and objectively computable, albeit fuzzily. We show that in this setting, context effects provide a reliable fast heuristic, and our subjects exploit it in the first seconds, leading to a large effect – up to 25 additional percentage points in choice share. However, in all situations where accurate choice does matter, the effect dwindles to near zero, for highly cognitively skilled participant (Experiment 1), or to a small size, for more representative consumers (Experiment 2).

If our results were to carry over to preference-based task, it would mean that context effects are best understood as a short-term heuristic, that might stick in the long term only in cases where subjects do not have the incentives, or the tools, to move on to slower, more deliberate thinking modes. This, however, is an open question that lies beyond the scope of the current paper. In this work we have provided, as a first step, initial evidence of a robust rise-and-fall pattern in a rather artificial setting. Whether the attraction effect and other context effects do indeed follow a rise-and-fall pattern and disappear when subjects face more realistic choices is therefore still an open question. However, we have developed a set of tools – a custom experimental design and an attuned modeling framework based on the MLBA – that makes this further explorations possible.

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A Experiment 1: Robustness to relative price variations

Figure 4 does not take into account the role of the relative price of the target and the competitor, as it aggregates data from choice sets in which it varies. This is justified because the distribution of the competitor price is symmetric around the situation of indifference, in which target and competitor have the same unit price. Nonetheless, the likelihood of observing an attraction effect may depend on the relative price of the target with respect to the competitor.

In Figure A.1 we compare, over the 20 seconds, the share of the target and the competitor when they have the same (dis)advantage with respect to one another, for the first (dashed) and all clicks (solid line). For instance, we compare the share of the target across all screens where the target is 15% cheaper to the share of the competitor across all screens where the competitor is 15% cheaper. These are *different* screens – and this is why curves in each panel of Figure 5 do not sum to 100%. But this allows us to compare apples to apples, i.e. comparing the dynamics of choice shares of options when they differ by role (target or competitor) but enjoy the same (dis)advantage in terms of value with respect to the other offer. We repeat this for all levels of relative price, thus look at the pure effect of being the target cleaned of relative price issues.

Figure A.1: Choice shares and difference in time, first and all clicks, by relative price

B Experiment 1: Alternative measure of attraction effect

In this section we provide evidence that our main result in Experiment 1 – the rise-and-fall pattern of the attraction effect over time – holds true using different measures of the attraction effect, overall and at different levels of the relative price of options. We exploit our control screens. For each screen with a decoy, the subjects had to complete a screen showing identical options but without a decoy. This was obtained in two different ways: simply eliminating the decoy option, and hence leaving the subjects with a choice over two options only (3vs2); or hiding the dominated nature of the decoy by making the decoy not directly comparable to the target (i.e., the “decoy” does not have the same size as the target, and does not perform any more the role of decoy, it is just another option, that happens to be worse than other options, 3vs3).

Figures B.1 and B.2 provide two examples of pairs of choice sets used to estimate the 3vs2 and 3vs3 measures.

Figure B.1: Example of choice sets used to obtain the 3vs2 AE measure

Figure B.2: Example of choice sets used to obtain the 3vs3 AE measure

For both comparisons (3vs3 and 3vs2), we use as a measure of the attraction effect the difference in the choice share of the target in presence vs in absence of a decoy.

We present here the same graphical evidence as in the main body of the paper. Figure B.3 shows the time pattern of this alternative measure of the attraction effect, by treatment, for the 3vs3 and the 3vs2 comparison, over all the screens, for first clicks (dashed) and including all revisions (solid line).

Figure B.4 shows the rise and fall patterns of the same measures by relative price difference, merging both treatments, for both comparisons and for first clicks and revisions. Overall, and with only

3vs3

3vs2

Figure B.3: Alternative measures of the attraction effect, by treatment

3vs3

3vs2

— All clicks - - First click

Figure B.4: Alternative measures of the attraction effect, by relative price of the target

small differences in some limited cases, the main result of Experiment 1 is replicated over two different implementation of this alternative measure.

C Detailed data on first and second clicks

C.1 Experiment 1

Table C.1 reports the choice shares and average response times for choices of target, competitor and decoy in the first and second choice, as well as the situation after the second click, for both treatments. A strong preference for the target appears in the first choice; moreover, most people choosing the decoy move to the target when clicking for the second time. This confirms that the target is disproportionately chosen in screens with a decoy in the early stages of the choice process, but then a revision process kicks in and participants switch away from the target, starting from the second click. Revisions play two main roles: they allow subjects having chosen the decoy to quickly switch, as shown in the table above mainly to the target; and allow subject having chosen the target, lured by dominance, to revise their assessment and move to the decoy.

	First choice		Revision			After revision	
	share %	time		share %	time		share %
Graphical							
Target	54.52	(4.05)	Competitor	37.12	(7.02)	Target	49.1
			Decoy	1.74	(4.5)		
			No revision	61.14	(-)		
Competitor	39.1	(4.37)	Target	29.96	(6.72)	Competitor	47.89
			Decoy	3.08	(4.84)		
			No revision	66.96	(-)		
Decoy	6.37	(3.47)	Target	63.51	(2.56)	Decoy	3.01
			Competitor	22.97	(5.87)		
			No revision	13.51	(-)		
Numeric							
Target	57.95	(4.88)	Competitor	39.62	(6.18)	Target	50.55
			Decoy	0.38	(2.37)		
			No revision	60.00	(-)		
Competitor	34.11	(6.18)	Target	29.45	(5.84)	Competitor	48.01
			Decoy	3.24	(6.54)		
			No revision	67.31	(-)		
Decoy	7.95	(2.72)	Target	72.22	(2.25)	Decoy	1.43
			Competitor	26.39	(3.05)		
			No revision	1.39	(-)		

Table C.1: Dynamics of revisions: choice shares after the first click, revisions upon the second click, and choice share after two clicks

C.2 Experiment 2

Table C.2 gives insights into the revision process followed by the subjects for each effect. The data for the Attraction effect very closely replicate the findings of Experiment 1: revisions mostly involve subjects having chosen the decoy quickly switching to the target, and subjects having chosen the target slowly reconsidering options and gradually switching to the competitor. Average response time support the same conclusion of two ongoing dynamics, with decoy choices being on average more impulsive, and switching from the decoy to the target exploiting visually focal dominance happening twice as fast as all other cases of switching between target and competitor, a choice that requires more careful comparison of the options. This clear pattern is inherent to the role of dominated option played by the decoy in the Attraction effect. No clear time or choice share pattern appears in the Similarity and Compromise data.

	First choice		Revision			After revision	
	share %	time		share %	time		share %
Attraction							
Target	54.83	(5.7)	Competitor	22.84	(6.77)	Target	54.04
			Decoy	0.71	(2.25)		
			No revision	76.45	(-)		
Competitor	37.61	(6.46)	Target	18.15	(6.53)	Competitor	43.91
			Decoy	2.43	(4.99)		
			No revision	79.42	(-)		
Decoy	7.57	(2.94)	Target	70.11	(3.24)	Decoy	2.04
			Competitor	20.11	(6)		
			No revision	9.77	(-)		
Similarity							
Target	30.23	(6.23)	Competitor	17.74	(6.5)	Target	30.19
			Decoy	20.74	(6.31)		
			No revision	61.52	(-)		
Competitor	35.34	(6.53)	Target	15.18	(7.37)	Competitor	36.94
			Decoy	11.63	(6.21)		
			No revision	73.19	(-)		
Decoy	34.43	(6.17)	Target	18.09	(6.14)	Decoy	32.87
			Competitor	16.58	(6.03)		
			No revision	65.33	(-)		
Compromise							
Target	31.02	(7.58)	Competitor	16.78	(7.07)	Target	32.23
			Decoy	17.48	(7.17)		
			No revision	65.73	(-)		
Competitor	27.77	(6.7)	Target	14.84	(6.66)	Competitor	26.81
			Decoy	28.44	(6.99)		
			No revision	56.72	(-)		
Decoy	41.21	(6.66)	Target	18.74	(8.04)	Decoy	40.95
			Competitor	14.21	(7.94)		
			No revision	67.05	(-)		

Table C.2: Dynamics of revisions: choice shares after the first click, revisions upon the second click, and choice share after two clicks

D Experiment 2: Robustness to relative price variations

Figure 7 does not take into account the effect of relative price differences between target and competitor. Figures D.1, D.2 and D.3 report the choice shares of each option in time, for each effect and by difference in the relative price of options. In the case of the AE, we again replicate a strong and robust rise and fall pattern for the Attraction Effect, at all levels of relative price of the target with respect to the competitor. In all cases, the effect shoots up in the first 5 seconds to then slowly fall, but, differently from Experiment 1, it does not reach zero for any level of relative price difference among options. On the other hand, the size of the attraction effect in case of indifference is much smaller than in Experiment 1.

For the other effects, subjects still respond to incentives but with an important share of decoy choices. This is partly by design, because the decoy has the same value as (at least one of) the other options in these effects.

We replicate the same rise and fall pattern for the similarity effect, but again only in the very first, not reliable seconds. The effect never converges to zero, but to a preference for similar options in the cases of indifference and when the target is more expensive, and to a preference for dissimilar options when the target is cheaper. A strong rise-and-fall pattern appears for the reverse compromise effect. This effect is all within the first click and not driven by revisions though, as revisions are not impacting the aggregate choice in a significant way.

Figure D.1: Attraction: choice shares and difference in time, first and all clicks, by relative price

Similarity effect

Figure D.2: Similarity: choice shares and difference in time, first and all clicks, by relative price

Reverse Compromise effect

Figure D.3: Reverse Compromise: choice shares and difference in time, first and all clicks, by relative price

E Control and demographics variables

Variables present for experiment 1 only:

Difficult: Was it difficult for you to make choices. Yes=1, No=0

Experience: How many studies did you take part in the past?

Motivation: Was it important for you to make the right choices? Coded 0-3 in order of importance.

Problems: Did you face any problems during this study. Yes=1, No=0

Understanding: Did you understand what to do in this study. Yes=1, No=0

AE: If two offers were of the same volume and the third was of a different volume, did you tend to prefer or avoid that of a different volume? 0: Prefer competitor, 0.5: Indifferent 1: Prefer target.

Confusion prone: Sum of answers to 9 questions adapted from [Walsh et al. \(2007\)](#), each graded from 1 to 5, in order of higher expressed confusion when shopping.

Loss aversion: When you decide to take a risk, do you think about the gains you could get, or the losses you could endure? 0-3 in order of tendency to think of losses.

Trust: Sum of answers to [Dohmen et al. \(2008\)](#)'s 3 item trust attitude survey, graded higher for higher expressed willingness to trust.

Shopping experience: Do you generally go shopping yourself? Yes=1, No=0

Budget holder: Are you in charge of your own budget? Yes=1, No=0

Variables present for experiment 2 only

Control questions trials: Number of times a subject tried (and failed) to validate the control questions screen. 0 if no mistakes; +1 for every unsuccessful attempt at validating the screen.

Variables present for both experiments

CRT score: Sum of correct answers to the standard CRT questionnaire ([Frederick, 2005](#))

Risk tolerance: Do you like to take risks, in general? (Give a number between 0 and 10. 0 if you avoid risks as much as possible, 10 if you always take the maximum risks)

Male: 1 if male, 0 if female.

Age: in years.

Income: Monthly post-tax family income, in categories graded as 500 for the category 0-1000 €, 1500 for the category 1000-2000 €, and 2500 for the category 2000-3000 €.

City size: Where did you live most of your life, in order of size, from countryside (0) to large city of more than 1 million people (4).

Education From no education (0) to advanced tertiary education (5).

Occupation Categorical variable: Worker, Student or Unemployed/retired.

Economics: Did you study economics? Yes=1, No=0

Table E.1: Control and demographics variables for both experiments

	Experiment 1						Experiment 2					
	Share	Mean	St.Dev.	Min	Median	Max	Share	Mean	St.Dev.	Min	Median	Max
Understanding												
Control Question trials							3.03	2.32	0	0		15
Difficult	0.24	0.43	0	0		1						
Experience	1.32	2.22	0	0		20						
Motivation	2.37	0.66	0	0		3						
Problems	0.03	0.16	0	0		1						
Understanding	0.98	0.13	0	0		1						
Personal Characteristics												
CRT score	0.92	1.1	0	0		3	0.68	0.88	0	0		3
Risk	5.45	2.25	0	0		10	5.73	1.97	0	0		9
AE	0.5	0.28	0	0		1						
Confusion prone	26.46	6.17	11	11		43						
Loss aversion	1.46	0.75	0	0		3						
Trust	3.41	2	0	0		8						
Shopping experience	0.86	0.34	0	0		1						
Budget holder	0.95	0.21	0	0		1						
Demographics												
Male	0.38	0.49	0	0		1	0.28	0.45	0	0		1
Age	26.8	8.23	18	18		63	45.28	12.08	24	24		67
Income	860.36	500.78	500	500		2500	1823.23	1198.17	500	500		8000
Education	3.77	1.16	0	0		5	3.62	1.38	0	0		5
Economics	0.42	0.5	0	0		1	0.2	0.4	0	0		1
City size	2.24	1.05	0	0		4						
Composition of the sample												
Student	53%						4%					
Unemployed/Retired	10%						28%					
Worker	37%						69%					

F Probability formulas

When considering what happens after a first choice of i at time t_1 , there are three possibilities:

1. j is observed to be chosen at t_2 or
2. k is chosen at t_2 , or
3. the choice of i is maintained, that is, there is no change in choices. This last possibility happens if either
 - (a) i was chosen at t_1 with j second, and i wins in the second race against j or j wins in the second race but after the time limit $T - t_1$.
 - (b) i was chosen at t_1 with k second, and i wins in the second race against k or k wins in the second race but after the time limit $T - t_1$.

1. For the first case, denote p_{ij} the probability that i is chosen first at time t_1 and a switch to j occurs at time t_2 . We obtain

$$p_{ij} = p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap t_{j2} = t_2) = p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ j \succ k) \times p(t_{j2} = t_2 \cap t_{i2} \succ t_2) \quad (1)$$

where

$$p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ j \succ k) = \frac{d_i^\alpha}{\sum d_1^\alpha} \frac{d_j^\alpha}{d_j^\alpha + d_k^\alpha} f(t_1), \text{ with } f(t) = \frac{\alpha}{\chi} \left(\frac{t}{\chi}\right)^{\alpha-1} \sum d_l^\alpha e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\chi}\right)^\alpha \sum d_l^\alpha} \quad (2)$$

$$p(t_{j2} = t_2 \cap j \succ i) = \frac{d_j'^\alpha}{d_i'^\alpha + d_j'^\alpha} g(t_2), \text{ with } g(t) = \frac{\alpha}{\chi} \left(\frac{t}{\chi}\right)^{\alpha-1} (d_i'^\alpha + d_j'^\alpha) e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\chi}\right)^\alpha (d_i'^\alpha + d_j'^\alpha)} \quad (3)$$

Note that $d_i' \neq d_i$ as those drifts result from a different set of comparison (between i and j) than the first choice comparisons (between i , j and k). Note again that t_2 is computed as the length of time between the first and the second choice.

2. For the second case, probability p_{ik} is computed in a similar way as p_{ij} .
3. The probability of the third case, which we denote p_{ii} , is more involved. We obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{ii} &= p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ j \succ k) \left[\int_{t_2} p(t_{i2} = t_2 \cap i \succ j) + \int_{t_2 > T-t_1} p(t_{j2} = t_2 \cap j \succ i) \right] + \dots \\ &\dots + p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ k \succ j) \left[\int_{t_2} p(t_{i2} = t_2 \cap i \succ k) + \int_{t_2 > T-t_1} p(t_{k2} = t_2 \cap k \succ i) \right] \\ &= p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ j \succ k) [p(t_{i2} > 0 \cap i \succ j) + p(t_{j2} > T - t_1 \cap j \succ i)] + \dots \\ &\dots + p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ k \succ j) [p(t_{i2} > 0 \cap i \succ k) + p(t_{k2} > T - t_1 \cap k \succ i)] \\ &= p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ j \succ k) \left[\frac{d_i'^\alpha}{d_i'^\alpha + d_j'^\alpha} + \frac{d_j'^\alpha}{d_i'^\alpha + d_j'^\alpha} e^{-(d_i'^\alpha + d_j'^\alpha) \left(\frac{T-t_1}{\chi}\right)^\alpha} \right] + \dots \\ &\dots + p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ k \succ j) \left[\frac{d_i'^\alpha}{d_i'^\alpha + d_k'^\alpha} + \frac{d_k'^\alpha}{d_i'^\alpha + d_k'^\alpha} e^{-(d_i'^\alpha + d_k'^\alpha) \left(\frac{T-t_1}{\chi}\right)^\alpha} \right] \end{aligned}$$

whereby $p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ j \succ k)$ and $p(t_{i1} = t_1 \cap i \succ k \succ j)$ are computed as per formulas 2 and 3.

G Choice sets for the simulations

	Target	Competitor	Decoy
Attraction	(1.5, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.5)	(1.50, 0.85)
	(1.0, 1.5)	(1.5, 1.0)	(0.85, 1.5)
Similarity	(1.5, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.5)	(0.95, 1.55)
	(1.0, 1.5)	(1.5, 1.0)	(1.55, 0.95)
Compromise	(1.5, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.5)	(2.00, 0.50)
	(1.0, 1.5)	(1.5, 1.0)	(0.50, 2.00)

Table G.1: Choice sets used for the simulations.

H Simulated choice shares and revisions

Option	First choice		Revision			After revision	
	share %	time	Option	share %	time	Option	share %
Target	34%	(6.72)	Competitor	19.39	(7.07)	Target	35%
			Decoy	11.49	(6.75)		
			No revision	69.12	(-)		
Competitor	36%	(6.74)	Target	15.07	(6.77)	Competitor	37%
			Decoy	14.09	(7.09)		
			No revision	70.84	(-)		
Decoy	30%	(6.61)	Target	19.44	(7.16)	Decoy	28%
			Competitor	16.14	(6.75)		
			No revision	64.42	(-)		

Table H.1: First choices, revisions, and final choice, for the similarity effect

Option	First choice		Revision			After revision	
	share %	time	Option	share %	time	Option	share %
Target	55%	(6.96)	Competitor	31%	(6.88)	Target	52%
			Decoy	0%	(-)		
			Stop	69%	(-)		
Competitor	41%	(6.82)	Target	28%	(6.74)	Competitor	46%
			Decoy	2%	(8.06)		
			Stop	70%	(-)		
Decoy	4%	(2.07)	Target	79%	(7.7)	Decoy	2%
			Competitor	3%	(6.77)		
			Stop	17%	(-)		

Table H.2: First choices, revisions, and final choice, for the compromise effect

I Bayesian priors and estimation procedure

Priors for the standard model

The prior distributions for parameters $p \in \{I, m, \lambda, \beta, stay\}$ is $\mathcal{N}_{>0}(1, 1)$ while $\gamma \sim \mathcal{N}_{>0}(2, 1)$. $\mathcal{N}_{>0}$ denotes the normal distributions truncated to the positive domains. $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \tau)$ is the normal distribution with mean μ and precision τ . Its standard deviation is $\sigma = \sqrt{1/\tau}$.

Priors for the hierarchical (mixed) model

The prior distributions for the model with mixed-effects is $p \sim \mathcal{N}_{>0}(\mu_p, \tau_p)$ for parameters $p \in \{I, m, \lambda, \beta, \gamma, stay\}$. We set $\mu_p \sim \mathcal{N}_{>0}(1, 1)$ for parameters $p \in \{I, m, \lambda, \beta, stay\}$ while $\mu_\gamma \sim \mathcal{N}_{>0}(2, 1)$. We set prior $\tau_p \sim \Gamma(1, 1)$ for parameters $p \in \{I, m, \lambda, \beta, \gamma, stay\}$. $\Gamma(\mu, \tau)$ denotes the gamma distribution with shape μ and rate τ . Its mean is μ/τ and its standard deviation is $\sqrt{\mu}/\tau$.

Estimation

We use R 4.0 to run RStan 2.19, a R interface to Stan (<https://mc-stan.org/>). Stan provides full Bayesian inference using the No-U-Turn sampler (NUTS) Hoffman and Gelman (2014), a variant of Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC). Estimates are based on 16 chains with 2000 warmup sample draws and 2000 post warmup sample draws per chain, resulting in 32000 post warmup iterations. There is no need to run more iterations unlike what is typical with for example the Metropolis–Hastings algorithm. That is because the NUTS sampler reduces autocorrelation within chains much faster than HMC, and thus obtains higher effective sample sizes per iterations. We assess convergence with the potential scale reduction factor (PSRF, see Brooks and Gelman, 1998). We also monitor the effective sample size (at least 10% of total post-warmup iterations) and visually inspect trace plots as well as pairs plots to check that chains mixed properly.

J Parameter estimates

Parameters	Exp 1: Graphical		Exp 1: Numeric		Exp 2	
	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI
I	1.90	[1.83;1.97]	1.49	[1.42;1.55]	1.31	[1.28;1.34]
γ	3.47	[3.20;3.70]	2.66	[2.48;2.85]	5.39	[5.18;5.60]
m	0.96	[0.89;1.03]	1.00	[0.93;1.08]	0.86	[0.83;0.89]
λ	0.49	[0.33;0.64]	0.28	[0.22;0.36]	0.99	[0.93;1.06]
β	0.68	[0.59;0.77]	1.54	[1.38;1.72]	0.85	[0.84;0.87]
α	1.47	[1.42;1.53]	1.38	[1.31;1.44]	1.46	[1.43;1.49]
LL	-287	[-294;-283]	-462	[-469;-457]	-5194	[-5204;-5188]
N	63		48		198	
Tasks	20		20		36	

(a) Model with first choices only

Parameters	Exp 1: Graphical		Exp 1: Numeric		Exp 2	
	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI
I	1.83	[1.77;1.88]	1.52	[1.47;1.57]	1.29	[1.27;1.32]
γ	2.72	[2.59;2.84]	2.70	[2.58;2.82]	4.65	[4.50;4.81]
m	0.99	[0.95;1.04]	1.00	[0.96;1.05]	0.92	[0.89;0.94]
λ	0.36	[0.29;0.43]	0.13	[0.09;0.19]	0.85	[0.80;0.89]
β	0.61	[0.56;0.67]	1.23	[1.07;1.40]	0.88	[0.86;0.89]
$stay$	0.96	[0.9;1.04]	0.93	[0.83;1.04]	1.04	[0.98;1.10]
α	1.47	[1.42;1.51]	1.35	[1.3;1.4]	1.48	[1.44;1.5]
LL	-1029	[-1059;-1022]	-925	[-932;-920]	-9442	[-9456;-9435]
N	63		48		198	
Tasks	20		20		36	

(b) Model with revisions

Table J.1: Parameter estimates

Table J.2: Summary statistics, individual parameter estimates, by experiment and treatment

Parameters	Exp 1: Graphical		Exp 1: Numeric		Exp 2	
	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI	Mean	90% CI
\bar{I}	2.33	[0.92;3.64]	2.20	[0.60;4.13]	1.96	[0.79;3.87]
$\bar{\gamma}$	3.90	[2.19;5.49]	3.89	[1.98;5.34]	3.29	[1.61;5.56]
\bar{m}	0.97	[0.83;1.07]	1.00	[0.81;1.15]	0.92	[0.70;1.14]
$\bar{\lambda}$	0.55	[0.22;1.03]	0.27	[0.15;0.38]	0.44	[0.21;0.82]
$\bar{\beta}$	0.73	[0.38;1.13]	1.14	[0.88;1.33]	0.72	[0.44;0.95]
\bar{stay}	0.93	[0.41;1.89]	0.82	[0.49;1.12]	1.10	[0.40;2.02]
N	63		48		198	

Figure J.1: Distributions and correlation of individual parameter estimates, by experiment and treatment

(a) Attraction effect.

(b) Similarity effect.

Figure J.2: Individual speed, precision and bias, by treatment
 Pearson correlation coefficient. Significance testing with Student's t-distribution. *** 1% ** 5% * 10%
 48

(c) Compromise effect.

Figure J.2: Individual speed, precision and bias, by treatment

Pearson correlation coefficient. Significance testing with Student's t-distribution. *** 1% ** 1% *5%

K Post-estimated choice shares and revision dynamics

We use estimates from our mixed model with revisions to predict the evolution of the shares of each option given the choice sets offered (Figures K.1 and K.2, to be compared with figures 4 and 7). We also provide tables outlining predicted dynamics of revisions (Tables K.1 and K.2, to be compared to those in appendix C).

K.1 Choice shares

Estimates translate in a consistent decrease in the attraction effects in both treatments of Experiment 1 and in Experiment 2, whereby the difference in share between the target and the competitor is lower after revisions than implied by first choices. This corresponds with the empirical findings. However, the level of attraction effect is underestimated, and the decrease in the attraction effect comes from an increase in the share of the competitor, while in reality the share of the target also decreases over time. Finally, the share of the decoy is overestimated.

Estimates also predict no similarity effect, and a reverse compromise effect. This is also consistent with findings from Experiment 2. Revisions do not significantly change the shares of each option, which corresponds to how neither of those effects exhibited any discernible *revision* dynamics overall in our Experiment 2.

(d) Attraction, experiment 1, graphical treatment (e) Attraction, experiment 1, numeric treatment

Figure K.1: Post-estimation prediction of shares over time, experiment 1

(a) Attraction (b) Similarity (c) Compromise

Figure K.2: Post-estimation prediction of shares over time, experiment 2

K.2 Revision dynamics

We consider now estimated revision dynamics for the attraction effect. The decoy, when chosen, is chosen faster than other options. Revisions away from the decoy are more frequent and faster than for other choices, and those revisions are towards the target. Additionally, revisions from the target to the competitor are more frequent than the converse. Those patterns correspond to those observed empirically, but are less pronounced. As for the similarity and compromise effect, we find no discernible patterns in revisions, which is consistent with our empirical observations. Finally, we find that the likelihood not to make a choice is estimated at between 1 and 3%, which is a bit higher than in reality.

Better fit with the data can be achieved by letting parameters of the model differ depending on whether we consider first choices and second choice. Running those regressions, we indeed find indications that speed and bias are higher for first choices (results not reported). This can explain the pronounced early peak in the share of target under the attraction effect that we observe in the data, followed by slow return to equal shares for the target and competitor.

	First choice		Revision		After revision	
	share %	time	share %	time	share %	
Target	45	(4.8)	Competitor	37 (5.45)	Target	45
			Decoy	6 (5.98)		
			Stop	58 (-)		
Competitor	44	(4.57)	Target	31 (5.64)	Competitor	48
			Decoy	5 (5.69)		
			Stop	64 (-)		
Decoy	11	(4.13)	Target	51 (4.71)	Decoy	7
			Competitor	27 (4.84)		
			Stop	22 (-)		

(a) Graphical treatment

	First choice		Revision		After revision	
	share %	time	share %	time	share %	
Target	48	(5.68)	Competitor	35 (5.61)	Target	48
			Decoy	3 (5.44)		
			Stop	61 (-)		
Competitor	44	(5.33)	Target	33 (5.62)	Competitor	47
			Decoy	4 (5.37)		
			Stop	63 (-)		
Decoy	8	(4.2)	Target	51 (4.62)	Decoy	5
			Competitor	29 (4.64)		
			Stop	19 (-)		

(b) Numeric treatment

Table K.1: Post-estimates of shares and revision dynamics in experiment 1, by treatment

	First choice		Revision			After revision	
	share %	time		share %	time		share %
Target	45	(6.54)	Competitor	28	(5.97)	Target	46
			Decoy	7	(5.99)		
			Stop	65	(-)		
Competitor	41	(6.37)	Target	27	(6.01)	Competitor	43
			Decoy	7	(5.85)		
			Stop	66	(-)		
Decoy	14	(5.64)	Target	41	(5.4)	Decoy	10
			Competitor	25	(5.43)		
			Stop	34	(-)		

(a) Attraction

	First choice		Revision			After revision	
	share %	time		share %	time		share %
Target	34	(6.63)	Competitor	17	(5.93)	Target	35
			Decoy	17	(5.86)		
			Stop	65	(-)		
Competitor	32	(6.63)	Target	19	(5.77)	Competitor	32
			Decoy	25	(5.92)		
			Stop	56	(-)		
Decoy	34	(6.67)	Target	19	(5.82)	Decoy	33
			Competitor	23	(5.95)		
			Stop	58	(-)		

(b) Similarity

	First choice		Revision			After revision	
	share %	time		share %	time		share %
Target	29	(6.5)	Competitor	21	(5.78)	Target	28
			Decoy	26	(5.76)		
			Stop	53	(-)		
Competitor	32	(6.54)	Target	18	(5.87)	Competitor	32
			Decoy	20	(5.78)		
			Stop	63	(-)		
Decoy	38	(6.61)	Target	18	(6.08)	Decoy	39
			Competitor	15	(5.91)		
			Stop	66	(-)		

(c) Compromise

Table K.2: Post-estimates of shares and revision dynamics in experiment 2, by effect

L Experimental instructions

L.1 Experiment 1

The original instructions were made up of a Power Point slideshow, using several visual cues as to make them appealing and easy to understand for the varied and heterogeneous population of subjects we faced. Here we provide a translation of all the words, plus the most relevant pictures.

General instructions

Welcome. This experiment is run by the Grenoble Applied Economics Laboratory (GAEL), part of the University Grenoble-Alpes (UGA).

The study is about individual consumption behavior. Instructions will be given to you as we go along. During the whole session, you will have to take some simple decisions. Nonetheless, should you have any difficulty or misunderstandings, do not hesitate to ask.

In order to protect your privacy during the session and in data analysis, you have been assigned a code. No data allowing us to identify you will be collected. Thus, it will be impossible for us to link your replies and decisions to your name. Data will be kept for statistical analysis and publication, but always in their anonymous format.

Communication between participants is not allowed, nor are comments about what should or should not be done during the experiment. Keep concentrated on your own computer screen and keep silence for the whole session. If you have a question, feel free to raise your hands and ask anytime.

You will see on your desk an envelope containing 10 € in cash, rewarding you for your participation. This sum is yours to keep. During the experiment, you will have the opportunity to gain extra money. The amount that you could gain will depend on the decisions you'll make during the session.

This study is composed of a learning phase followed by a payoff-relevant phase. Before the start of each phase, instructions will be given. A new phase will start only after all participants have completed the previous phase. This session will not exceed one hour and thirty minutes.

Do you have any questions?

Your Task - buying gas

You have to fill with gasoline a jerrycan that can contain 3 liters. You have a budget of 5 € to fulfill the task, and a limited time.

Your gain consists in all the money that you will not have spent on the gasoline. Your task is hence to find the cheapest offer on the market. Unfortunately, you will not have access to the price per liter. Each gas station will show you its offers as a quantity of gas, and the price asked for this quantity.

The quantities are shown [*graphical*: by means of a visual representation] [*numeric*: in liters]

This is an offer. The quantity of gasoline [*graphical*: represented by the pink-colored part] is displayed on top, and the price for the shown quantity below.

With this information, you can make an estimation of the cost of the 3 liters. The price of offers, as well as the quantities offered for that price, are randomly drawn. The drawings are independent – that is, the prices of the different offers have no particular relationship with one another.

There are two types of gas stations: those displaying two offers and those displaying three. In both cases, the offers are independent from one another. Your task is always the same: finding the least expensive offer.

1.6 litres

1.92€

1.92€

Figure I.1: An offer

1.92€

3.00€

1.6 litres

2 litres

1.92€

3.00€

Figure I.2: A two-offer choice set

1.92€

1.62€

3.00€

1.6 litres

1.2 litres

2 litres

1.92€

1.62€

3.00€

Figure I.3: A three-offer choice set

Figure I.4: The offer used in the computation example

Once you have chosen an offer, the computer computes automatically the total price that you will have to pay for the three liters. You keep the change: your payoff consists of all the money that you have not spent on the gasoline. To maximise your payoff, you have simply to find the cheapest offer.

Example of payoff computation: if you choose this offer:

- for a price of 1.35 € you will buy 1.5 liters.
- this quantity corresponds, in this example, to half of the target quantity
- your total expenditure will hence be $2 \times 1.35 = 2.7$ €
- your payoff if you choose this offer is hence of $5 \text{ €} - 2.7 \text{ €} = 2.3 \text{ €}$

This task will be repeated 40 times, with different offers, in different gas stations with two or three offers. At the end of the experiment, 5 screens will be randomly drawn. Your total payoff will be the sum of the payoffs obtained in each of these 5 screens.

How do we record your choices

Attention! we will be using a specific process to keep track of your choices.

You will have 20 seconds to make a choice. During these 20 seconds, your choice will be recorded at each moment. You can change your mind as many times as you wish. A bar on the bottom of your screen will inform you on the remaining time.

Now suppose your choice pattern looks like this [*graphical: same screenshot with graphical stimuli*]:

At the end of the task, the computer will randomly draw a second between 1 and 20. The payoff-relevant choice will be the one that was active at the randomly drawn time. If no choice had been made at the randomly drawn time, the computer will assign you a random offer.

Let us consider some cases.

Case1 the time chosen by the computer is 9 seconds. The payoff-relevant choice is A.

Case2 the time chosen by the computer is 18 seconds. The payoff-relevant choice is B.

Case3 time chosen by the computer is 6 seconds. No choice! the payoff-relevant offer will be randomly drawn among A, B and C.

Figure I.5: An example choice pattern

Summing up: as long as you made no choice, you risk that the computer selects for you an offer you do not like. It is hence in your best interest to make a fast, possibly provisional, choice, to prevent the random draw from determining your result. You can then change your mind afterwards, as many times as you like.

Learning phase

We will first let you practice on the task. You will face 4 practice screens. At the end of the 4 screens you will be shown a summary of all your choices and potential gains for these screens. This phase is not payoff relevant: the payoffs that you will see on the summary screen are just meant for training purposes.

Payoff-relevant phase

You will now start the payoff-relevant phase. You will face 40 different screens. At the end of the experiment, 5 screens will be randomly drawn. Your total payoff will be the sum of the payoffs obtained in each of these 5 screens.

L.2 Experiment 2

For experiment 2, we aimed at a shorter version of the instructions, but the content is otherwise very similar to that of experiment 1. The original instructions were made up of a Power Point slideshow, using several visual cues as to make them appealing and easy to understand for the varied and heterogeneous population of subjects we faced. The subjects received also a one-page A4 print of the text with the most relevant figures, on their cubicles in the lab. Here we provide a translation of the printed version.

Figure I.6: Three cases for the random draw

Your task

In this experiment, you will have to imagine that you have to fill a tank of petrol as cheaply as possible. You have a budget of 6 Euro to do this. There are several competing offers at the petrol station.

The problem is that these competitors do not give you their price per litre, but the price for a given quantity of petrol. This information allows you to estimate the cost of filling up for each competing offer.

Your gain will be everything you don't spend on petrol, i.e. your budget (6 Euro) minus the total price you pay to fill up. Your aim is to find the cheapest offer

What is the cheapest option per litre?

You will face a choice between different offers 42 times, on choice screens with two or three offers. At the end of the study, 8 choice screens will be drawn for each of you by the computer. Your total winnings will be the sum of the winnings from each of these 8 choice screens.

Procedure to record your responses

We will use a special process to record your answers.

You will have 20 seconds to make your choice. During these 20 seconds, your choices will be recorded at each moment. You can change your mind as many times as you like.

When the 20 seconds are up, the computer will draw a second between 1 and 20. The answer taken into account to determine your winnings will be your current choice at that second. If no answer was recorded at the second drawn, the computer will select a random offer for you.

Any choice, not just the final choice, has a chance of being the valid choice for payment; until you have made a choice, the computer may randomly select an offer you do not like.

So you had better make a choice very quickly, at least provisionally. You can always change your mind afterwards, and as many times as you like. The longer you stay with a choice, the higher the probability that it will be drawn for payment.

Experiment timeline

You will first answer control questions to check your understanding of the task. You can only continue with the experiment after you have answered all these questions correctly.

After that, there will be two unpaid trial phases: one consisting of choice screens with 2 offers, and one consisting of choice screens with 3 offers. For each of these phases, you will get detailed feedback on your choices over time, the second one drawn, and the payment that would result from it.

You will then proceed to the 42 choice screens that count towards your payoff. 8 of these screens will be drawn at the end of the experiment to determine the payoff. You will receive the sum of the earnings on these 8 choices.

So always be careful, any of your choices can determine your payoff!

Finally, we will ask you a short series of additional questions.

Your payment will be made directly to you in cash at the end of the session.

M Details of the creation of offers and choice sets

M.1 Experiment 1

Subjects were exposed to 20 expenditure minimization tasks with three options and a decoy. Across tasks we varied the relative price of the target and the competitor. Intermingled with those 20 screens subjects faced also 20 control screens, with no or not obvious decoys, used to compute the alternative *3vs2* and *3vs3* measures.

In our design each option is fully described by two attributes: the unit price of gasoline and the amount of gasoline sold. The price that was shown to the participants was then simply computed as unit price times amount displayed. We started by creating the 20 main choice sets of three options as follows:

- We drew four different unit prices for the target from a uniform distribution in the open interval $[0.6, 1.4]$, with a granularity of 5 cents. This unit price was then multiplied by 1.2 to obtain the price of the decoy. The decoy is *always* 20% more expensive than the target. The unit price of the competitor was the unit price of the target multiplied by 0.85, 0.95, 1, 1.05, or 1.15. The competitor is always cheaper than the decoy, but in varying degrees; and it might be cheaper or more expensive than the target. We thus obtain $4 \times 5 = 20$ main choice sets.
- For each of these 20 choice sets we then drew the amount of gasoline of the target and competitor from the set $\{0.9, 1.3, 1.7, 2.1, 2.5\}$ (liters), without replacement. We assign to the decoy the same amount of gasoline as the target.
- When draws of unit price and amount of gasoline resulted in two offers in a choice set having identical shown prices (i.e., *unit price* \times *amount*), then this choice set was discarded and the procedure repeated so as to avoid having price decoys – i.e. a dominance relation on the shown prices. Dominance relations could then only appear in the amount of gasoline dimension.

To generate control screens, we followed two procedures. Half of the screens were dedicated to the *3vs2* measure, by simply removing the decoy. The other half was dedicated to the *3vs3* measure, by drawing a random size for the decoy, thus breaking the dominance relationship. The position of the options of each screen was randomized once, and this random order of options was then applied to all participants.

A detailed list of the 20 choice sets and their respective 20 controls, in their graphical and numeric versions, as well as a collection of screenshots are available on the OSF page of this paper <https://osf.io/xr28d/>.

M.2 Experiment 2

Subjects faced 42 expenditure minimization tasks. In 6 tasks subjects faced only 2 options, two tasks with indifference and four with different values across options. This was done to assess their accuracy

in absence of any context effect. The remaining 36 tasks were subdivided equally among the three context effects. Out of the 12 screens for each context effect, four covered situations of indifference between the target and the competitor and eight situations in which one of the two options had a higher value.

For each effect, we concentrated on a limited, carefully chosen number of offers. This is in contrast with Experiment 1 where offers were randomly built from a set of building blocks. This was done because we had a lower number of screens available to estimate each effect, to ensure that the new measure worked well, and in order to be able to better estimate the MLBA-R model (see below section 4). We created the offers, ran extensive simulations, and estimated the model on the simulated data over several iterations before settling to the final choice sets.

Screens are based around a first, basic set of four options (depicted in Figure 6, a). A target and a competitor sit on the same indifference line, and to these we add two decoys. With these four options we can build two screens to get a single measurement of the context effect. We then add two more options, sitting on a new, higher indifference line to the north-east of the original set, with a 10% unit price decrease, and provide those with two decoys; and two options on a new, lower indifference line to the south-west with a 10% price increase, also with two decoys. Decoys are always 15% more expensive than their target. In order to have good comparability across effects, we use the *same* base offers for all three effects; all that changes across effects is the position of the decoys, that follow the pattern laid out in Figure 6. To avoid too many repetitions of the exact same figures, though, base offers were nudged 5% away in different directions for the Similarity and compromise effect, with respect to the baseline Attraction Effect offers.

The R script used to generate the offers, the choice sets, and the stimuli, alongside with its complete output, is available on the OSF page of the paper <https://osf.io/xr28d/>.